

**IJESA PRONOUNS IN THE
SOCIO-CULTURAL CONTEXT**

BY

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ABSTRACT

Studies in pronoun usage in social interactions in some languages and dialects are common in sociolinguistic literature. However, such studies have not been able to address a number of questions, one of which the present study has addressed. Therefore, the aim of this study is to provide answers to the question of who uses what type of pronouns, to whom and when. Through this we would be able to ascertain the socio-cultural variables guiding pronoun usage in Ijesa.

The sociology of language and ethnography of communication approaches were adopted as the research methodology. While the ethnography of communication approach claims that cultural rules are needed for word or sentence interpretation, the sociology of language approach argues that variations in language use are contingent on sociological factors of age, wealth, sex, education and

social status. The data that were used in this study were drawn from interviews, participant observations and recording of utterances.

The present study has shown that the social functions of first person singular pronoun include refusal, innuendoes, power, questions, responses to questions, ownership, pride, surprise, threat, affront, underrating and confirmation. It has, also, been shown that first person plural pronoun could be adopted by a single person to show play and mockery. Also, the use of singular and plural pronouns in social interactions does not in some cases reflect the socio-cultural values of either disrespect or deference as claimed by previous studies. Similarly, the general belief among grammarians and sociolinguists that any of the singular pronouns can only serve as a mode of address for a single person has been faulted. This cultural phenomenon in the Ijesa pronoun usage has been proved to be in agreement with the Hebrew, Greek and Arabic systems of address either in the temple, church or mosque especially during preachings.

Again, misunderstanding, hatred, jealousy, patronage, support, cooperation, favour, newness, and appreciation can serve as bases for pronoun usage. These findings are additional to the sociological factors identified by the previous studies. Furthermore, the factors of rejection, acceptance, disdain, questions, appeal, pride, threat, discord, reminder, inference, mockery, responses to questions, affront, refusal, confirmation, underrating, social stigma, information, surprise, deception, ownership, innuendoes, lack of sufficient knowledge, stupidity and mistaken identity can also influence the choice or use of either the second or the third person singular or plural pronouns.

This study bestrides the areas of grammar and sociolinguistics. It has proved the insufficiency of grammatical analysis as explanation of the nature of language as suggested by Chomsky (1965) and Katz (1966). Instead, we now know that the knowledge of a language or of its dialect, in this case the Ìjèsà dialect of Yoruba, is a composite of

the knowledge of structure and use in the socio-cultural context. This is what underlies the concept of communicative competence.

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to the IKOTUN family.

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CERTIFICATION

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CHAPTER ONE

1.1 THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to investigate the patterns of choice of pronouns in relation to culture among those who speak the Ijèsà dialect. Studies in the ethnography of communication and sociology of language will provide the theoretical background for the study. We will also consider both formal and informal methods of elicitation of information to find out how socio-cultural factors determine the choice of Ijèsà pronouns in social interactions among people who use the Ijèsà dialect. But, before this is done, it is important to consider some historical issues about Yoruba as a tribe and Yoruba as a language.

1.2 YORUBA AS A TRIBE

Yorubá is a nomenclature, which refers to the amalgamation of the Yorubá sub-ethnic groups. The consensus of opinion that the

Yorùbá sub-ethnic groups have a common descent from Oduduwa ~~is~~ ~~debatable~~ in view of the political and ethnic boundaries which ~~existed~~ among the Yorùbá sub-ethnic groups before the British and ~~church~~ missionary incursions into the south-western part of Nigeria. However, the linguistic, religious and cultural evidence that is available lends credence to the claim that the Yorùbá sub-ethnic groups must have had a common origin (see Idowu 1962, Okediji and Okediji 1970, Yemitan and Ogundele 1970, Vidal 1986).

These groups occupy a land area that lies between the parallels 5.86° and 9.22° north and between 2.65° and 5.72° east (see Okediji and Okediji 1970). It is bounded in the north by Kwara State and it has a common boundary with Benin Republic, a French territory in the west and with Edo State in the east in Nigeria. There are also Yorùbá ethnic groups in both Kwara State and Republic of Benin (see Appendix B).

It will be recalled that the Western State created by Yakubu Gowon in 1967 is now split into Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo, and Ekiti states. Lagos, which is also part of the west, was excised from the west during the London constitutional conference of 1953. The state creators then did not ignore the fact that members of the Yorùbá ethnic groups live in Kwara, Kogi and parts of Edo State. With the transfer of the Nigeria's capital seat from Lagos to Abuja, the removal of the 1953 excision of Lagos from the West could be assumed¹.

1.2 YORUBA AS A LANGUAGE

The word Yorùbá is also used to refer to standard Yorùbá and sometimes to its dialectal variants. However, the variants of the Yorùbá language are also referred to by the names of the sub-ethnic groups namely; Oyo, Ijẹṣa, Ekiti, Ondo, Akurẹ, Owo, Egbá, Ijebu to mention a few, instead of Yoruba. (see Adetugbo, 1967).

The Yorùbá language has tonal features (see Bamgbose, 1990). Compare, for example, igbá (calabash), igbà (time), igbá (garden-

two hundred) *igbá* (rope) (see also Okediji and Okediji, 1970; Salami, 1987). From the historical evidence, one can say that the Yorùbá dialectal variants are naturally used and informally learnt while standard Yorùbá is formally learnt in schools. This position is confirmed by the several attempts made by governments, organisations and scholars to design an acceptable orthography for the standard Yorùbá language (see Crowther, 1852; Bowen, 1858; Bamgbose, 1967; Afolayan, 1969).

It will be recalled that the church missionary society (CMS) played a significant role through Bishop Ajayi Crowther to have the Yorùbá language written down. This was in 1844 in Sierra-Leone (Okediji and Okediji, 1970). But before Crowther, Bowdich had written down the Yorùbá numerals. Bowdich collected his data in Ashanti, Ghana. (see Arohunmolase 1987). Also, Clapperton, Kilham, J. Raban and E. Norris (cited in Arohunmolase, 1987) contributed to the development of Yorùbá as a written language.

Between 1844 and 1856, Crowther translated the English Bible into Yorùbá while Gollmer also translated the books of the decalogue, the book of common prayer and St. Matthew's gospel into Yorùbá. Between 1857 and 1862, King translated some Greek scriptures into Yorùbá. In 1859, Townsend started the publication of the first Nigerian newspaper called 'Ìwé Ìròhin' (News book) (see Mustapha, 1986). Similarly, between 1885 and 1952, there were several news publications in Yorùbá (for detailed information, see Arohunmolase, 1987 pp. 1-16). However, the Yorùbá orthography that was in use between 1852 and 1862 had English influence.

The orthographic situation between 1963 and 1966 was not significantly different from the orthography that was in use between 1852 and 1962. In 1963, UNESCO set up a committee to recommend a suitable orthography for the Yorùbá language. Members of the committee agreed that authors should use the spellings of the words written below in their writings. Nwòn (they), aiyé (world), ènyin

...~~on~~ obinrin (male) obinrin (female) on (he/she/it), àyà (chest) aiya
 ...~~fun~~ fun a (give him/her/it) rán a (send him/her/it) pín i (share it).

We can raise two questions from the 1963 committee's work.

- (1) How could ayé (world) which has mid-high tone contour with two syllables of equal strength, duration and amplitude become aiyé (world) a word, which has mid-mid-high tone contour with three syllables?
- (2) How could vowels u, a, and i, which are not nasal vowels replace nasal vowels in 'fun' (give), 'ran' (send) and 'pin' (share) as pronouns in the object position?²

In January 1966, a committee headed by Archdeacon S.A. ~~Change~~ was set up by the Western State of Nigeria to look into the possibility of recommending a Yorùbá orthography that would be standard for the whole region. In its recommendations, the committee resolved the linguistic ambiguity raised in question two and left the question one unanswered. We could now have 'fún un' (give

(share it) 'pín in' (share it) and 'rán an' (send him/her/it) and not 'fún
 (give him/her/it), 'pín í' (share it) and 'rán a' (send him/her/it). The
 changed committee on Yorùbá orthography of 1969 (by the Western
 State Government of Nigeria) introduced the use of hyphen into words
 that have nasal vowels. For example, òfònòn (a house rat) tiníntínín
 (robin) to mention a few should now be written as 'òfòn-òn' (a house
 rat) tin-in-tin-in (robin).

The committee that succeeded in removing letters which did not
 have any grammatical or lexical function in Yorùbá spellings was the
 committee set up by the Federal Government of Nigeria. This was in
 1974. With the development of standard Yorùbá between 1817 and
 1974, the linguistic situation in Yorùbá-speaking areas has become
 diglossic (Ferguson, 1959, 1966). Standard Yoruba and the dialectal
 variants are functionally kept apart. While standard Yoruba is the H
 variety, each of the dialectal variants is the L variety. So, while
 standard Yorùbá is learnt in schools and used as a lingua franca

among the Yorubá ethnic groups, Yorubá dialects enjoy currency in their immediate linguistic environments.

1.1 IJESA

The Yorubá ethnic group whose dialect is the focus of this study occupies an area called Ijesa-land. The area is in the south-eastern part of Osun State. The Ijesa land shares a common boundary with Oragbo Central and Ede East Local Government areas at Kajola, Surupe Local Government at Ipetu-Ile area, Ondo State in the east, Ekiti State in the south and Ife Central Local Government area in the west (see Appendix C).

Ijesa-land is made up of many towns and villages. Some of these are: Ilesa, Ipetu-Ijesa, Ijebu-Jesa, Erinmọ, Osu, Erin-Oke, Erin-Ode, Ibokun, Ere, Iperindo, Imesi-Ile, Otan-Ile, Ifewara, Idominasi, Ilase, Esa-Oke, Esa-Odo to mention a few. The Ijesa-speaking area is made up of six local government councils. Two of these are in Ilesa, namely, Ilesa West, with the headquarters at Ereja, and Ilesa East with

the headquarters at Iyemogun. In the North, Ijebu-Jesa is the headquarters of Oriade local government, while Ibokun is the headquarters of Obokun local government. There are two local government councils in the south: Atakumosa East has Iperindo as its headquarters, while Osu remains the headquarters for Atakumosa West (see also Omikunle, 1992/93).

Ijesa-land covers over 2200 square kilometres of land and it is about one quarter of the total land mass of Osun State. Politically, Ijesa people see Ilesa as their capital. Ilesa, which is known, among the Ijesa people as a place of refuge, had maximum security during the Yoruba inter-tribal wars because it was the Ijesa warlords' base. Ilesa is situated on longitude 4° 35 east of Greenwich and latitude 7° 30 north of the equator (see Aluko, 1993).

Furthermore, Ilesa is about 30 kilometres from Osoybo, the Osun State capital. All Ijesa people are in a derogatory manner called 'Osomáalo' (people who squat). The word 'Osómáálo' (squatting) is

the shortened form of 'Oṣò ni màá lù gboó mi lóníí. (I will squat to collect my money today). The use of this word reminds one of the business activities of the Ijesa people in the past. The population of the Ijesa people is 379638 (see Osun State Gazette No 25 Vol. 84 of 15 April, 1997).

The Ijesa people have a distinct speech form called Ijesa. The dialect has some variants. For example, the English sentence "I will beat you" will be "Mọ kàn a lù ó" in Ipetu-Ijesa area and "Màá lù ó" in Ijesa area. However, the pronominal and the cultural systems remain the same in all these areas. The word Ijesa may therefore mean an ethnic group called Ijesa, an area occupied by them, the culture of the people and the dialect spoken by them.

1.4 TONE

One conclusion we can draw from previous studies on tones in Yoruba is that tones are indispensable to Yoruba. However, there is no consensus on how tones function in the language. Four claims have been

usually made by Bamgbose (1967:4-7, 1990:41-46) with regard to tone in Yoruba. First, there are three tones in Yoruba; these are high tone (/), mid tone (-) and low tone (\). Second, there is another tone called assimilated low tone which is a variant of the low tone. Third, each syllable has a tone. The fourth claim is that tones help to distinguish words that have the same orthographical form but different meanings. Some of the examples that are given to support the functions of tones in Yoruba are:

bè (jump)

bé (to be forward)

bé (ask for pardon)

Akinlabi (1985:62), on the other hand, argues that there are two tones in Yoruba, the high tone and the low tone. The mid tone, according to Akinlabi (1985) is stress and not a tone. One question which Akinlabi does not consider in his argument is whether there is a difference between the duration, strength and amplitude of the high,

the low and the mid tones. In Yoruba, the three tones have the same duration, strength and amplitude. For example,

Oṣìyò = [-˧]

(The owner of salt)

Therefore, the mid tone is still a tone and not stress because none of the three syllables sounds stronger than any other syllable. Similarly, Bamgbose's claim that tones help to distinguish words that have the same orthographical form has been challenged by Akinlabi (1985:115). According to Akinlabi, tones cannot help to distinguish the two examples below from each other after elision:

wá + imò = wámò (look for palm leaves)

wá + imò = wámò (look for knowledge)

In reply to these examples, Bamgbose suggests the use of an assimilated low tone for a place where a vowel with a low tone has been elided. So, wámò (look for knowledge) should be written as "wá.mò" (look for knowledge). But, the question Bamgbose does not

Does Yoruba orthography allow the use of dot in Yoruba writings? It will be recalled that the Yoruba orthography committee's report of June 15, 1969, does not approve Bamgbose's suggestion for the use of dot in Yoruba orthography. This is the reason why dot is not used in Yoruba writings (see A report on Yoruba Orthography (1969)). Additionally, Bamgbose's contribution to Yoruba studies does not explain how we can handle examples where the object or subject noun phrase does not start with a vowel that has a low tone.

Four sets of examples are provided below: 1, 2, 3, and 4, 5, 1 and 2, 4 and 5.

- 1 Kọ orin (sing a song)
- 2 Kọ orin (write a song)
- 3 Kọ ebè (make heaps)
- 4 Kọ oúnjẹ (dish food)
- 5 Kọ oúnjẹ (reject food)

We can make four deductions from these examples. First, the verb 'Ka' in examples 1, 2, 3, and 4 should be written as 'Kó' but because of the object noun phrase which has a mid tone as its initial syllable, the verb 'Ka' is now 'Ko'. For example, it may be 'kó' (dish (it)). This is the answer to the question 'Sé kí n ko óunje?' (Do I dish food?). Secondly, if the verb 'Ko' in example 5 is used as an intransitive verb it would be 'Kò'. For example, it may be 'ó kò' (He/she rejected) in response to the question, 'Njé ó ko óunje?' (Did he/she reject food?). Another observation is that even though each occurrence of the verb 'Ka' in examples 1-5 has the same phonological representation because of the objects, the meanings of the verbs are different. It is, therefore, not possible for tones to distinguish between 1 and 2, 4 and 5 as they have different meanings though with the same phonological representations or forms.

Furthermore, tones cannot distinguish examples 6 and 7, 8 and 9, 10 and 11, from each other and examples 12 - 15 from one another.

16 jù (burn/burnt)

17 jù (dance)

18 ní (soft)

19 ní (pour)

20 mí (fire)

21 mí (lice)

22 ní (tie)

23 ní (roof)

24 ní (pain)

25 ní (drain)

It is therefore evident from these examples that tones cannot distinguish words that have the same spellings from one another in some cases in standard Yoruba. This tonal limitation or phenomenon is not only limited to standard Yoruba, it can, also, be observed among some Yoruba dialects such as Ijesa, Ife, Ekiti, Akure and Ondo. However, the prominence of the high tone in the negative

is higher than the prominence of the high tone in the

~~Sentence:~~ Olá yẹ mí (I am due for honours) →

Oláyemí → [-/-]

~~Sentence:~~ Olá yẹ mí (I am not due for honours) →

Oláyemí → [-/-]

Olú lọ → [-/-]

(Olú went)

Olú lọ → [-/-]

(Olú did not go)

Olú lọ → [-/-]

(Olú is not going)

Olú lọ → [-/-]

(Olú will not go)

~~Positive Sentence:~~ Adé ye ifá (The crown befits the
god of divination) →

Adéyefá → [-/-]

~~Negative Sentence:~~ Adé ye ifá (The crown does not
befit the god of
divination) →

Adéyefá → [-/-]

~~Positive Sentence:~~ Ifá şe öleş (Ifa (god of divination)
has not been lazy) →

Ifaşöleş → Fášöleş → [^/-]

~~Negative Sentence:~~ Ifá şe öleş (Ifa (god of divination)
has been lazy) →

Ifaşöleş → Fášöleş → [^/-]

~~Positive Sentence:~~ Adé gbõn mí rẹ (The crown has not left me) →

Adégbõnmírẹ → [-Λ]

~~Negative Sentence:~~ Adé gbõn mí rẹ (The crown has left me) →

Adégbõnmírẹ → [-Λ]

~~Positive Sentence:~~ Awó şe iká (A priest of Ifa divination has not done wickedly) →

Awóşiká → [-Λ]

~~Negative Sentence:~~ Awó şe iká (A priest of Ifa divination has done wickedly) →

Awóşiká → [-Λ]

From these examples, empirical evidence shows that 'Fáṣòlẹ', 'Adégbõnmírẹ' and 'Awóşiká' in the negative are mostly in use. To further support this claim, on 11 September, 2001, one of the

...of programmes on the Ondo Radio station pronounced the
 ...of the secretary to the state government as 'Adégbòmíré' (the
 ...has left me) instead of 'Adégbòmíré' (the crown has not left
 ... The use of the negative names is traceable to one of the
 ...of tones in these dialects.

ELISION AND CONTRACTION

Studies in the area of elision and contraction in Yoruba show
 that elision and contraction are common phenomena in Yoruba.
 (1990:44-45) claims that part of the rules for elision of
 and contraction of two or more words which affect tones

When there is a contraction between a verb and a noun the
 elision of a vowel will mean the elision of a tone. For example,

wá + igbá → wágbá

(Look for calabash)

In this example, vowel [i] is elided.

When there is a contraction between two nouns the elision of a vowel will also mean the elision of a tone. For example,

Oni + apá → alápá

(owner of arms)

When a contraction occurs between two words, elision must affect the vowel that has the low tone. This vowel must either occur finally in the first word or initially in the second word.

The use of apostrophe is however recommended by Bamgbose (1990) to show that a vowel is elided. For example,

bi + èjì → bé'jì (give birth to twins)

yóò + wá → yó'wá (He/she will come)

máà + ké → má'ké (Do not cry/shout or he/she must not cry/shout)

There are two questions for Bamgbose (1990:44-45). In writing, is a contraction possible between 'yóò' a grammatical word or a tense marker and 'wá' a verb or 'máà' a negation and 'ké' a verb? Is the use

Furthermore, in agreement with the recommendation of the 1966 committee on Yoruba orthography? While the generally acceptable contraction 'bí èjì' (give birth to twins) can be contracted as 'béjì' (give birth to twins) and not as béjì words like 'yóò' and 'máà' cannot be contracted with verbs. So, in writing, contractions like 'bí èjì' and 'máà' may not be acceptable as far as Yoruba orthography is concerned. Again, if the use of apostrophe is in agreement with the recommendation of the 1966 committee on Yoruba orthography, apostrophe should be placed before vowel [é] and not after vowel [é]. Therefore, 'bí + èjì' should be contracted as 'bí'èjì and not as 'béjì'.

Furthermore, Akinlabi (1985:100) and Bamgbose (1990) accept the fact that when a contraction occurs between a verb that has a single syllable and a noun that has two syllables the result will be a word that has two syllables. For example,

1	ṣ	+	ṣé	→	ṣṣé or ṣṣé (do a work)
2	k	+	ilé	→	kólé (build a house)
3	b	+	èjì	→	béjì (give birth to twins)
4	k	+	èkò	→	kékò (learn how to read and write)
5	n	+	ipín	→	nípín (have a share)
6	w	+	èkò	→	wékò (look for knowledge)

Although Bamgbose's suggestion favours; *ke.kò, ní.pín, wé.kò*, we have pointed out that the use of dot is at variance with Yoruba orthography approved for usage. (see A report on Yoruba orthography 1969:61). Akinlabi and Bamgbose's claim will however hold for examples 1-3 but will not hold for examples 4-6 because even Yoruba speakers pronounce when a contraction occurs between these words are:

4. kò + èkò → kékòò (learn how to read and write)

5. mí + ipín → nípín-ín (have a share)

6. wá + èkò → wékòò (look for knowledge)

The question which is of interest to Oyelaran (1971) and Akinlabi (1985:29) studies is: Are tones features of vowels? While Oyelaran (1971) argues that tones are features of vowels Akinlabi (1985:29) says they are not. For example,

wá + èkò → wékòò

Vowel 'e' in 'èkò' has a low tone but after elision and contraction vowel 'e' has a high tone. Oyelaran (1971) claims that the high tone of vowel 'a' does not mean elision of the high tone and that the high tone is transferred to vowel 'e' which remains after contraction (see also Bamgbose, 1990). Akinlabi (1985:29-36) argues that tones are not features of vowels because if they are vowel 'a' and the high tone must be deleted. None of Oyelaran (1971), Bamgbose

and Okunribido's (1985) suggestions can be deemed as correct. Tones are features of vowels but after elision and contraction they must affect both the vowel and the tone. Secondly, tones are inseparable from vowels as tones cannot appear in isolation without being accompanied by vowels. So, the production of a vowel must be with the vowel and its sound quality which may be high, low or

ASSIMILATION

Assimilation refers to "a system whereby the vowel of one of the words that meet at a word boundary changes its form or sound and becomes identical with the vowel of the other word" (see Okunribido, 1978:154, Bamgbose, 1990:47). Awobuluyi (1978:154-155) gives the following examples to support assimilation in the Yoruba language.

1. ilé iwé → ilé èwé (school)
2. ori Òjó → oró Òjó (Òjó's head)

3. ilé Ọjó → iló Ọjó (Ọjó's house)
 4. ilé Ọlá → iló Ọlá (Ọlá's house)
 5. iwé Dàdà → iwé e Dàdà (Dàdà's book)

Obayemiye's (1978:154-155) findings can be challenged from different angles. First, if there is assimilation between a noun and a vowel there must also be contraction. So, 'ilé' and 'iwé' will be 'ilé' (school) after assimilation and contraction and not 'ilé èwé' after assimilation alone. Bamgbose, (1967:50, 1990:48-50) must also consider the factors of assimilation and contraction before a noun and another noun can become a word. Another observation is that in standard Yoruba, assimilation is not possible in examples 2, 3, 4 and 5. The morphological rules do not also allow 'Dàdà's book' to be written as 'iwé Dàdà'. The rules favour 'iwée Dàdà' and not 'iwé Dàdà'. But this research work would have wished that the Yoruba orthography recommendation be reviewed in favour of 'iwée Dàdà'.

In the Yoruba language the word 'Dada' is a noun which does not require a qualifier for 'iwé' (book). The argument Awobuluyi (1978:154-155) would have advanced in favour of 'iwée Dada' is that when a vowel with a high, low or mid tone ends a sentence is qualified by a noun that starts with a consonant, the vowel that ends the qualified noun must be lengthened (see also Awobuluyi 1989:125). This lengthening is not assimilation as claimed by Bamgbose (1978:154-155). For example,

Father's house - Ilée baba

Father's land - Ilèè baba

Father's farm - Okoo baba

Therefore, there cannot be assimilation between 'iwé and Dàda'

in Standard Yoruba.

Furthermore, Bamgbose's (1990:48) contribution to assimilation in Standard Yoruba shows that assimilation is possible between the

verb 'mú' (take) and the noun 'éwá' (ten) (see also Akinlabi 1999). For example,

mú + éwá → mééwà (take ten)

However, 'mééwà' (take ten) should have been written as 'múéwá' and not as 'mééwà' if the Yoruba morphological rules are strictly adhered to. It is also not assimilation alone that is responsible for 'mééwà' but assimilation and contraction. We can, therefore, assume that the Yoruba numerals are in three categories when there are assimilation and contraction or contraction between the verb 'mú' (take) and the Yoruba numerals. For example,

1. mú + èjì → mééjì (take two)
2. mú + èta → mééta (take three)
3. mú + èrin → méérin (take four)
4. mú + èjọ → mééjọ (take eight)
5. mú + èsán → mééṣán-án (take nine)
6. mú + éwá → mééwáá (take ten)

II. $m + \text{òkánlá} \rightarrow \text{mòókánláá}$ (take eleven)

III. $m + \text{ogún} \rightarrow \text{mógún}$ (take twenty)

IV. $m + \text{ogóji} \rightarrow \text{mógóji}$ (take forty).

Examples 1 - 4 are in the first category while examples 5 - 7 are in the second category. The third category comprises examples 8 and 9. The difference in examples 1 - 4 and examples 5 - 7 lies in the fact that in example 5 - 7 each of the second vowels in the nouns is pronounced and this is in fulfilment of the Yoruba morphological rule which says whatever that is pronounced must be written down. Another observation from examples 1 - 9 is that while assimilation and contraction occur in examples 1 - 7 contraction occurs in examples 8

Additionally, there is a difference between examples 1 - 9 and examples 10 - 16 below:

III. $m + \text{èji} \rightarrow \text{méji}$ (two)

III. $m + \text{éta} \rightarrow \text{méta}$ (three)

ṣ	m	+	èrin	→	mérin (four)
ṣ	m	+	èjo	→	méjo (eight)
ṣ	m	+	ésán	→	mésán-án (nine)
ṣ	m	+	èwá	→	méwáá (ten)
m	m	+	òkànlá	→	mókànláá (eleven)

While each of examples 1 -9 is a verb, each of examples 10 - 16 is a numeral qualifier or a post modifier. For example,

Mo kó iwé méwáá (I packed ten books)

O m eyin méji (You bought two eggs)

But the question that has not been addressed is whether consonant 'm' can be added to 'ogún' (twenty) or 'ogóji' (forty). In Yoruba 'ogún' (twenty) and 'ogóji' (forty) are some of the Yoruba vigesimal numerals and consonant 'm' cannot be added to any of the vigesimal numerals. Ikotun (2000:53) recommends the use of 'ipò' (position) in addition to any of the vigesimal numerals before it can be used as a post modifier.

YORUBA PRONOUNS

Adetugbo (1967:105-106) carried out a study on standard Yoruba and its dialects. In the study, Adetugbo (1967) used linguistic evidence to explain the geographical placement or classification of standard Yoruba and its dialects. The study, also, covers the pronouns of standard Yoruba as well as the pronouns of the Yoruba dialects (see also Abiodun, 1992:101-102). The information in the tables below shows Adetugbo (1967) and Abiodun's (1992) claims about the Yoruba pronouns. Table A is for Adetugbo (1967) and Table B is for Abiodun (1992).

	Long Pronouns	Short Pronouns	Pronouns in the Object Positions
First person	Émi	Mo, me, ma	Mi
Second person	Éwo		O
Third person	Óun		identify with preceding vowel
Fourth person	Áwa	A	Wa
Fifth person	ín-in éin	In	In
Sixth person	íon	On	On

	Emphatic Pronouns	Non-emphatic Pronouns	Pronouns in the Object Positions	Pronoun Qualifiers
First person singular	Émi	Mọ/Mo	Mi	Mi
Second person singular	Úwọ	O	Ọ	Rẹ
Third person singular	Ọun	Ó/Ó	Un	Rẹ
First person plural	Ìa	A	A	Ria
Second person plural	Ìn-in	In	In	Rin-ín
Third person plural	Ìn-ọn	Ọn	Ọn	Rin-ọn

In this research work, we will consider the information provided by Alenrode (1992:101-102) on Ijesa pronouns. However, in usage, contraction or assimilation and contraction can occur between any of the words like 'sé', 'ni', 'tí', 'bí' 'kí' and any of the second and third person singular and plural pronouns. For example,

Sé + O → Sọo (Did you)

Se - O	→	Ṣọọ (Did you)
Ti - O	→	Tóọ (If you)
Ti - O	→	Tọọ (If you)
Igbà + O	→	Ìgbọọ (When you)
Igbà + O	→	Ìgbọọ (When you)
Ki + O	→	Kóọ (That you)
Ki + O	→	Kọọ (That you)

In the first example, vowel 'e' is removed when assimilation occurs between 'sé' and 'o' and 'o' is doubled though the resultant word retains the high tone on 'e' to get the word 'Ṣọọ' (Did you) after contraction. This shows that the tone of the vowel that occurs finally in the first word must be retained when there are assimilation and contraction between particles and any of the second person singular pronouns.

Furthermore, contraction between words like 'se', 'ti', 'ni', 'bi' and any of Ijesa third person singular pronouns 'ó' and 'ò' is possible. For example,

Sé	+	Ó	→	Şó (Does he/she)
Sé	+	Ó	→	Şó (Does he/she)
Ti	+	Ó	→	Tó (If he/she)
Ti	+	Ó	→	Tó (If he/she)
Ki	+	Ó	→	Kó (He/she should)
Ki	+	Ó	→	Kó (He/she should)
Ìgbà	+	Ó	→	Ìgbó (When he/she)
Ìgbà	+	Ó	→	Ìgbó (When he/she)

Similarly, assimilation and contraction can occur between words like 'ti', 'bi', 'ki', 'sé', 'ni' and the Ijesa pronouns 'a', 'in' and 'an'. For example,

Ti	+	a	→	Táa (If we)
Bi	+	a	→	Báa (If we)

Ká	+	a	→	Káa (We should)
Şá	+	a	→	Şáa (Did we)
Lá	+	a	→	Laa (And we)
Tín	+	in	→	Tín-in (If you)
Bín	+	in	→	Bín-in (If you)
Kín	+	in	→	Kín-in (You should)
Şín	+	in	→	Şín-in (Are you)
Ìgbà	+	in	→	Ìgbà-in (When you)
Tì	+	òn	→	Tì-òn (If he/she/they)
Bì	+	òn	→	Bì-òn (If he/she/they)
Kì	+	òn	→	Kì-òn (He/she/they should)
Şì	+	òn	→	Şì-òn (Did he/she/they)

(For discussion on n and l alternation, see Awobuluyi, (1978)).

The following words can be contracted;

ni	+	in-in	→	nìn-in (And you)
ni	+	òn-òn	→	nòn-òn (And he/she/they)

lgbà - òn-òn → lgbòn-òn (When he/she/they

It is also possible for the pronominals in both varieties to occur in the subject position. But, when the pronominals occur in the object position there could be elision of vowel and contraction between the pronominal and the pronominals. For example,

○ ri èmi (He/she saw me)

○ rimi (He/she saw me)

Vowel 'e' with its low tone is elided and 'rí + èmi' become 'rími'. If the word 'náà' is added to 'èmi', the resultant word after the contraction will be 'rémi' and not 'rími'. For example,

○ ri èmi náà (He/she saw me too)

○ rémi náà (He/she saw me too)

If there is a contraction between the verb 'rí' and 'ùwọ', vowel 'u' and not 'u' will be elided though the low tone on 'u' will be retained with the high tone on vowel 'i'. The word will be 'rúwọ' and

The sentence 'ó rúwọ' is not acceptable in Ijesa unless the word 'náà' is added. So, the sentence will now be;

Ó rúwọ náà

(He/she saw you too)

The sentence 'ó róun' is not acceptable as far as Ijesa syntactic structures are concerned. But, if the word 'náà' is added then the sentence becomes an acceptable sentence. For example,

Ó róun náà (He/she saw him/her too)

We can also have the following sentences where other pronouns are shown.

Ó ría (He saw us)

or

Ó ría náà (He saw us too)

Ó rín-in (He saw you)

or

Ó rín-in náà (He saw you too)

Ò rín-ọ̀n (He saw him/her/them)

or

Ò rín-ọ̀n náà (He saw him/her/them too)

The word 'àti' can be used to join either two or more

pronominals together in a sentence. For example,

Èmi àti ùwọ́ á sẹ́

(You and I will do it)

Èmi, ùwọ́ àti ọ̀un á sẹ́

(You and I will do it)

It is also possible for elision and contraction to occur between the word 'àti' (conjunction) and any of the pronominals that is placed

immediately after it. For example,

Ìwọ́ àtẹ̀mi ló wá

(It is you and I that came)

When contraction occurs between the word 'àti' and any of the pronominals, the vowel 'i' of the word 'àti' will be elided. For

Èmi àti ùwọ (You and I)

Èmi àtùwọ (You and I)

Similarly, a contraction is possible between words like 'şé', 'tí', 'kí' and any of the pronominals. For example,

Şé + èmi → Şémi (Am I?)

Şé + ùwọ → Şúwọ (Are you?)

Kí + in-in → Kín-in (You too)

Kí + ia → Kía (We too)

Kí + òun → Kóun (He/she too)

It will be recalled that there is a disagreement between

Adetugbo (1967), Bamgbose (1967, 1990) and Ogunbowale (1970)

on whether pronouns and pronominals should be regarded as

pronominals. While Adetugbo (1967) and Ogunbowale (1970) regard

and pronominals as pronouns, Bamgbose (1967, 1990) states that pronominals are not pronouns. However, Bamgbose's (1967, 1990) study recognises that pronominals share some qualities with number and person with pronouns.

In our present study, we will consider pronouns and pronominals in both subject and object positions as pronouns. This is because the pronoun distributional characteristics which are useful for the present study of pronoun usage in the sociocultural context are present in the pronominals.

One question which has not been considered in this section and is of importance to the present study of pronoun usage in the sociocultural context is whether there is any relationship between the characteristics and the Ijesa culture. The answer to this question shall be the focus of the next section.

THE STATUS OF IJESA PRONOUNS IN RELATION TO IJESA CULTURE

Bock (1962) defines culture as "a set of inter-related, partially arbitrary expectations, understandings, beliefs or agreements, shared by the members of some social group, which can be shown to influence (or to have influenced the behaviour of some members of that group". Goodenough (1966) argues that "a society's language is an aspect of its culture". Adetugbo (1967) claims that culture has two parts - the verbal and the non- verbal.

Bauman and Sherzer (1975) claim that the verbal aspect of culture is concerned with the cultural rules by which the social use and non-use of a language is organised. In relation to the Ijesa cultural rules for choice of pronouns, the Ijesa pronouns can be divided into two groups. The first group consists of pronouns that do not carry a mark of deference when each of the pronouns is used for a single person. The second group comprises pronouns that carry a mark of

when each of the pronouns is used for a single person (see Oluwalana, 1992).

The information in the tables below shows the standard or basic pronouns and their variants.

TABLE 1 IJESA PRONOUNS THAT DO NOT CARRY A MARK OF DEFERENCE WHEN EACH OF THE PRONOUNS REFERS TO A SINGLE PERSON

SINGULAR	STANDARD FORM	
	Pronouns	Pronoun Qualifiers
1st	Mo, èmi	Tèmi, mi
2nd	O, ùwọ	Tiè, rẹ
3rd	Ó, òun	Tiè, rẹ

Some sentences are given to provide examples on how these pronouns are used in relation to culture.

Mo gbe

(I (singular) carried it)

O ki

(He/she (singular) greeted him/her (singular))

Emi lo ni

(It is I (singular) who have it)

Uwo ni mo ri

(It was you (singular) I saw)

Oun naa de

(He/she (singular) too arrived)

Usa temi ree

(This is my (singular) yam)

Usa ti ree

(This is your (singular) yam)

O ri mi

(He/she (singular) saw me (singular))

O ri o

(He/she (singular) saw you (singular))

Q10000

(It is your (singular) money)

Q10001

(It is his/her (singular) money)

TABLE 2: IJESA PRONOUNS THAT CARRY A MARK OF DEFERENCE WHEN EACH OF THE PRONOUNS REFERS TO A SINGLE PERSON

SINGULAR	STANDARD FORM	
	Pronouns	Pronoun Qualifiers
In	In	Rin-in, tin-in
On	On	Rin-on, tin-on

Below, are some sentences.

In lo

(You (plural) went)

On lo

(He/she (plural) went)

Mo noko rin-in lánáá

I saw your (plural) vehicle yesterday

Mo rulé rin-on

I saw his/her (plural) house

Furthermore, the use of pronouns in relation to culture is not only a sociolinguistic phenomenon that is witnessed among the Ijesa dialect speakers, it is, also, a common occurrence among the standard Yoruba, Egba, Ijebu, Ekiti and Igbomina dialect speakers (see Adeniran, 1990; Abiodun, 1992; Oyetade, 1995; Olateju, 1997).

However, one area of disagreement between Abiodun (1992) and Oyetade (1995) is whether deference as a criterion for pronoun usage is inherent in the Yoruba culture. Abiodun (1992) does not favour inherence of deference in the Yoruba culture. Abiodun's (1992) position is contingent on two reasons or factors. First, the Yoruba traditional religion and literature do not make use of deference in their address systems. Secondly, some Yoruba dialects

Owo, Ondo and Oyi do not have deference in their address

Oyetade (1995) claims that the use of deference in pronoun is inherent in Yoruba and not foreign based as claimed by (1992). According to Oyetade (1995) "if the use of honorific pronouns in Yoruba were the result of foreign influence, it would be expected to come from a language like French rather than English. Even though English is the source of the bulk of loanwords in Yoruba, it cannot be the source of this phenomenon, as the honorific pronoun was no longer in use in English at the time of contact with the peoples of Nigeria" (For language interference, see (1987; Ahukanna, 1990; Ikotun, 1999).

In support of Oyetade's (1995) claim, we can argue that it is not the Yoruba traditional religion or literature that does not make use of deference in its address system, some other world religions such as Judaism, Christianity and Islam do not have deference in their

address systems (see The Holy Bible, The Holy Quran). So, either the Yoruba religion or literature may not serve as a good reference point for deference in address systems.

Again, it is not true that deference is not shown in address systems in the Yoruba literature. The examples which Abiodun (1992) presents as evidence in support of deference in address systems in standard Yoruba, Ijesa, Ekiti and Igbomina are taken from some Yoruba literature books and translated to Ijesa, Ekiti and Igbomina. These literature books are written by Fagunwa (1950:49), Isola (1978:15), Yemitan (1980:22) and Akinola (1984:88).

It can also be stated that it is not compulsory that a standard variety of a language and other dialects of the language be guided by the same cultural rules in their address systems. Several differences between standard Yoruba and its dialects in the areas of phonology, morphology, syntax and semantics can lend credence to this claim. For example, the Ijesa sentence 'Mèé wòde' (I am looking

will mean 'Mèé relé' (I am going home or to the house) in the Ijesa dialect.

The standard Yoruba sentence 'Kò dùn' (It is not sweet) will be translated as 'Ó níta' in the Idogun/Ifira dialect. Both Ikare and Idogun/Ifira dialects are spoken in Ondo state. 'Kín ni?' (What is it?) in standard Yoruba will be 'Emi ni?' in the Ikirun/Inisa dialect (for further discussions on phonology and morphology see Oyelaran, 1977; Oyetade, 1983).

However, is there any justification for the present study of Ijesa dialects in the socio-cultural context? We will consider this question in the next section.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

When one person speaks to another person, the selection of linguistic forms is governed by the relationship between the speaker and his addressee (Brown and Ford, 1966). In Ijesa traditional society, there are norms that guide behaviour patterns in social

In the Ijesa dialect certain formal devices are employed to show certain relationships to others and our attitudes towards them. In this study, we are interested in the use of pronouns in relation to culture. We want to find out the socio-cultural factors which determine the choice of Ijesa pronouns in social interaction among people who use the Ijesa dialect.

But, before now, some attempts have been made by some scholars to investigate the use of second and third person singular and plural pronouns in relation to culture among standard Yoruba as well as Yoruba dialect speakers. For example, Abiodun's (1992) study of pronoun usage among some Yoruba dialect speakers shows that plural pronouns, when used, can serve as indicators of power, rebuke and humour. Abiodun (1992), also, shows that the factors of presence and non-appearance of the addressed during the time of address are responsible for the choice of either plural or singular pronouns.

Oyetade's (1995) sociolinguistic analysis of address forms in Yoruba shows that the standard Yoruba pronouns can be grouped into two main categories. The first category, when used, carries a mark of respect and can show either honour to second or third person singular. The second category, when used, does not carry a mark of respect and can show dishonour either to second or third person singular (see also Akindele, 1990). Olateju's (1997) study of pronoun usage among the Ijebu and Egbá people shows that the use of singular pronouns can express contempt, anger or intimacy while the use of plural pronouns can express admiration, respect and polite distance.

However, there are some issues which these previous studies have not addressed and which are of interest to the present study of pronoun usage in the socio-cultural context. These include:

- (a) to find out whether or not there are factors that can influence the use of first person singular pronoun 'èmi'

- (1) and first person plural pronoun 'ia' (we) or any of its variants in social interactions;
- (b) to find out whether it is in all cases that a distinction can be drawn between the social functions of singular and plural pronouns in social interactions.
 - (c) to find out whether there are other factors that can influence the use of second or third person singular or plural pronouns in social interactions; and
 - (d) to determine what the remote causes are for pronouns being used as factors of power, courtesy, rebuke, humour, admiration, polite distance, contempt and anger.
- It is the belief of the present study that unless these issues are discussed on pronoun usage in the socio-cultural context ~~will~~ remain inconclusive.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

In this study, the use of Ijesa pronouns in the socio-cultural context will be carried out. The specific objective is to investigate the preferences of choice of pronouns in relation to culture among those who speak the Ijesa dialect. It makes more interesting sociolinguistic study of a choice issue by people who master the dialect.

NOTES

- i A personal discussion with Professor S.A. Ekundayo of the Department of English, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, in 1998.
- ii See A report on Yoruba Orthography 1969:iv-ix.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

INTRODUCTION

This chapter discusses some concepts in sociolinguistics such as participants, topics, attitudes or behaviour, modes of ethnography of communication and sociology of language. It will be recalled that the present study deals with pronoun usage in a sociocultural context. The chapter is expected to provide a theoretical background for the study.

ETHNOGRAPHY OF COMMUNICATION

One of the central aims of ethnography of communication is the connection between language and culture. This opinion is clearly embraced by Goodenough (1966), Levi-Strauss (1966), Fishman (1974), Bauman and Sherzer (1975) and Saville-Troike (1982). These scholars claim that cultural rules are needed for word or sentence

For example, Goodenough (1966) remarks that a country's language is part of its culture. He argues that in the course of learning a language and how to use the language, every human being acquires the bulk of his culture.

Similarly, Levi-Strauss (1966) says that the sociologist is in a better position to inform the linguist of customs, positive rules and prohibitions, which explain the persistence of certain traits of language or the instability of terms or groups of terms. Fishman (1972) also argues that language and society reveal various kinds and degrees of patterned co-variation and that sociology of language is one of the approaches that make the marriage between language and culture an inevitable phenomenon. Although, Bauman and Sherzer (1975) distinguish language from culture, they claim that ethnography is concerned with patterns and functions of speaking that emphasize the use of language in the conduct of social life.

Furthermore, Saville-Troike (1982) claims that ethnography of communication is the way communication within a speech community is patterned and organized as systems of communication and the ways in which they interact with all other systems of culture (see also Firth, 1966). But the opinions expressed by Hymes (1966), Levi-Strauss (1966), Fishman (1968), Bauman (1975) and Saville-Troike (1982) are at variance with the Katz (1966) approach to the study of language.

Katz (1966) denies any correlation between language and culture and claims that language and culture are independent. In his approach to the study of language, Katz argues that the process by which a speaker interprets each sentence is a compositional process in which the meaning of any syntactically compound constituent of a sentence is obtained as a function of the meanings of the parts of the sentence. It is important to explore studies which resolve or seek to remove the differences between Katz (1966) and others.

Ekundayo's (1976) study is a critique of Katz's approach to the study of language. Ekundayo (1976) disagrees with Katzian opinion and claims that the process of semantic interpretation is not as straightforward as the Katzian compositional framework suggests and that the cultural aspects of sentence production in language use will make the Katzian model, which is totally devoid of necessary cultural information, inadequate for the semantic component of a Yorùbá grammar. If we were to interpret the sentence; 'Owó pò lówó mi' (I have much money) on the basis of Katzian theory, it would mean that the person in question has much money whereas what Ekundayo (1976) and a native speaker of Yorùbá are saying is that the person in question has no money. While we accept Ekundayo's position, we are aware that there are sentences in Yorùbá that may not require any element of culture for their interpretation.

It can therefore be argued that Katzian (1966) denial of any correlation between language and culture in some cases cannot be

limited. For example to interpret the Yorùbá sentence 'Mo fẹ̀ lẹ̀ sójà' (I want to go to the market), one needs only the Yorùbá grammar and the lexicon and not the Yorùbá culture. There are still other works or studies in other languages that are in support of culture as a tool for sentence interpretation. We shall now look into some more of this.

Adams' (1966) study is an example of this. Adams (1966) argues that each culture defines its own presentational meanings (see also Hymes, 1974). In his study of expressive communication in an Egyptian village, Adams observes that if a speaker is a friend then whatever he says is generally accepted as friendly even if the content of his message is not complimentary. On the other hand, if the speaker is an enemy then everything he says, even if it is conciliatory, is suspect. One problem with the study is that the study does not tell us how genuine enemies and genuine friends can be identified in a given situation or time.

Frake's (1966) study is on the diagnosis of disease among the ~~people~~ of Mindanao in southern Philippines. Although, the focus of ~~the~~ study is social structure among the people, Frake discovers that ~~the~~ ~~importance~~ to culture is needed in order to participate in ordinary ~~conversations~~ especially in the area of terminologies such as folk ~~remedy~~ and medicine. We can also say that it is not only ordinary ~~conversations~~ that the people would need culture to participate in the ~~people~~ might also need culture to participate in conversations that are ~~not~~ ordinary.

Haas' (1966) study is on word taboos. Haas' paper contains two ~~pieces~~ of information on language studies. First, she shows that the ~~Indians~~ who are resident in Oklahoma avoid the use of the Creek words which bear some phonetic similarity to the four letter words of English especially when white people are around. Secondly, Haas ~~observed~~ that Thai students studying in the same area tend to avoid certain words of their language, which bear a phonetic resemblance

English obscene words. It is indicated that the words are usually avoided only when English speakers are around, although, Haas notes that the avoidance of such words stems from the Thai students' uncertainty about the propriety of using the words because of their knowledge of English.

We are of the opinion that what is of significance to sociolinguistics or ethnography of communication in the study lies in the Thai students teaching each succeeding group of newly arrived students about the taboo and the way its avoidance is kept alive from year to year. We can therefore say that the uncertainty about the usually avoided words should have been removed as a result of the mastery of the English Language by the older generations of the Thai students, and that it should be possible for the usually avoided words to become usually unavoided.

Nadel (1966) discusses morality and language among the Nupe people. In the study, Nadel (1966) epitomizes semantic limitations, in

...sees culture as a factor for the Nupe peoples' adoption of some
...as replacements for some names meant for some parts of the
...body or some activities between men and women in public.
...example, sexual matters are not freely discussed in public and the
...is to guide against moral decadence among the young ones.
...can say if this is the case with sexual matters; it may not mean
...the importance of grammar and lexicon would not be considered
...other areas that have nothing to do with morals.

The essence of Conklin (1966) and Frake's (1972) studies also
...the importance of culture in sentence interpretation. Conklin
(1966) claims that methods of modifying the normal patterns of
...speech for purposes of entertainment or concealment are perhaps
...universal and that where such practices occur, considerable cultural
...importance must be associated with the contexts in which they occur.
Conklin's position is informed by his findings about the sociocultural
...lives of the Hanunoo people of Philippines. The findings show how

...part of language description may help to define a major
...differentiation within the wider social structure.

Similarly, Frake's (1972) findings on how to ask for a drink
among the Subanun people indicate that a stranger needs more than
grammar and a lexicon to know what kinds of things to say in what
message forms to what kinds of people in what kinds of situations.
We can argue that this position may not be required in all
communications of social life or language use.

Fasold (1990) argues that the correctness of any word or
sentence depends on the time, place and participants in the speech
events in which they occur. He, also, claims that the factor of context
is important for any truth-based semantic theory. The study of the use
of context, according to him, helps in making inferences about
meaning. It can be argued that if Fasold's (1990) position is true of
sentences that require culture for interpretation, Fasold's (1990)

is also true of sentences that require a grammar and a lexicon interpretation.

We believe that grammar alone cannot explain the intricacies present in a language like Yorùbá. The understanding of the relationship between the culture of a society and the language the uses helps to bring into focus the hidden aspects of a language which grammar cannot explain. In our present study of pronoun usage we shall try to find out the extent of the influence of the Ijesa culture on the sociolinguistic aspects of Ijesa pronouns.

II DOMAINS, PARTICIPANTS AND TOPICS

The framework for successfully carrying out result oriented sociolinguistic studies is the concern of Fishman (1972), Ervin-Tripp (1973) and Hymes' (1974) studies. These studies seek to answer Fishman's (1972) question: who speaks what language to whom, when and why. The framework suggested by them comprises participants,

topics, culture and languages. All known sociolinguistic studies have given credence to these criteria.

For example, Ferguson (1959, 1966) uses the factors of participants, domains and topics in reporting the language situation in various countries. Three deductions can be made from his theory of choice. Choice of a language or dialect is contingent on participants. This claim is supported by the example of the Baghdad language situation where the christian Arabs speak a christian Arabic dialect when talking among themselves but speak the general dialect when talking in mixed groups. The factors of function, lexicon, grammar, phonology, acquisition, prestige, standardisation, literary heritage and stability determine and distinguish the higher variety from the lower variety of either genetically related or unrelated languages. Acquisition of formal education guarantees the use of the higher variety of a language.

Ferguson's (1959, 1966) theory of diglossia has been questioned by sociolinguists.

Gambhir (1983) argues that Ferguson's definition of diglossia is too static and sees the diglossic situation of a language like Arabic as flexible and changeable rather than stable. In support of Gambhir's opinion, Wardhaugh (1986) recalls the history of the language situation in Greece before and after 1975. He says that there were two varieties of the Greek language namely Katharevousa, the H variety, and Demotic, the L but with the return to constitutional government in 1975, Demotic, the L variety, became the official language in 1976 thereby replacing the Katharevousa, the H variety. Wardhaugh (1986) therefore argues that the continuity of the language situation in any of the Arab countries is based on the fact that standard Arabic has several dialectal variants and any attempt by any of the regional groups to replace the standard Arabic with any regional variety will undermine the unity of the Arab-speaking countries.

Furthermore, Gambhir (1983) observes that while some elites use the higher variety in both formal and informal domains, there are also many who are not in control of the higher variety and thus use the lower variety in formal and informal domains. Gambhir's claim is more tenable than Ferguson's especially when the two varieties in question are genetically related and have mutual intelligibility. For example, as a result of long detachment from the rural areas by some intelligents for socio-economic reasons, some of the highly educated people whose mother-tongue is the L variety may decide to use the H variety in both intra and inter-group meetings (see also Gumperz, 1966). Some of the illiterates too who have not acquired sufficient knowledge of the H variety may use the L variety in both formal and informal domains.

Gambhir (1983) also observes that in formal domains, it is likely that some non-literate speakers who are socially conscious would try to incorporate some syntactic and lexical features of the

... variety in their speech. Gambhir's position reminds one of the
... of children of highly educated Nigerians who, at the
... age, can speak standard English even when they can
... read nor write the language (see also Bloomfield, 1966). As
... of exposure too, non-literate users can successfully
... some syntactic and lexical features of the H variety in
... speech.

Similarly, Ikotun's (1995) study of code choice and language
... in Idoani community shows that diglossia as advanced by
... can only exist when languages or codes under study do not
... mutual intelligibility and participants or interactants cut across
... and language groups.

Akere's (1982) study of language use and language attitudes in
... a Yorùbá sub-urban town, indicates that language use in the
... speech community involves a choice between Ijebu and Eko
... in the community's linguistic repertoire. The two conclusions

can be drawn from Akere's work are that, the dialects of a language may not be used in inter-group interactions and the use of a standard language and the standard language can be used in inter-group interactions. The first conclusion is at variance with Gumperz's (1983) conclusion that some people use the dialect of a language in inter-group interactions.

Blount (1979) argues that in any bilingual or multilingual society, the study of the bilingual's choice of code in relation to topics is important. It is this study of the codes in relation to topics that will determine which among the codes is used for which topic. For example, Blount finds that in the data examined, in the non-urban towns, there seems to be no case of parents and guardians who are primary school teachers introducing English language into the home as a second language or as a replacement for the mother-tongue as against what happens among the elite families in urban towns.

We can say that two major reasons are responsible for Ure's results. First, the groups studied have common linguistic background and since there are no strangers among the groups, there is an inclination for the people to use their mother-tongue more frequently. Secondly, the locality, which is sub-urban, places the use of the mother-tongues in a better position because the majority of the people, if not all, who use the local languages are illiterate or find it easier to express themselves in their mother-tongues for some reasons.

Equally, one major issue that is central to the studies of Heye (1979) and Parasher (cited in Gambhir, 1983) is the discovery of the functional domains of the bilingual societies. From the two studies, we can say that the factor of functional domains is a crucial one which guarantees the survival of a mother-tongue in the face of overwhelming qualities of an official language in multilingual communities.

Oke's (1972) study of language choice in the Yorùbá-Edo border area is based on domains and participants. Oke identifies two language groups at Ido-Ani in Ondo State. The Iyayu people who are bilingual and the Amusigbo people who are monolingual. He says the Iyayu people will only speak the standard Yorùbá language with outsiders. We are of the opinion that the continuity of the Yorùbá language would not have been possible among the Iyayu people when the outsiders will not speak the language to the younger generations.

However, there are some questions which the works or studies cited could not answer and which we will consider in our present work. The first is whether culture has any role to play in language use in social interactions and secondly, what role attitudes have to play in language use in social interactions. The third is whether domains, participants and topics make provisions for the study of the way in which language is used to express or interpret real intentions in particular situations especially when the actual words used may

to mean or may mean something different. The present study, which focuses on pronoun usage in relation to culture will seek to answer the question of who speaks what pronouns to whom, when and

MODES OF ADDRESS

When one person speaks to another person, the selection of linguistic forms is governed by the relationship between the speaker and his addressee (Brown and Ford, 1966). There are sociolinguistic studies, which support Brown and Ford's (1966) findings. One of such studies is Brown and Gilman's (1968) study of pronoun usage among the French language users.

The essence of Brown and Gilman's (1968) findings points to the fact that sociological factors are factors that can help to reflect the language situation in any community. The study recognises social factors, physical strength, wealth, age, sex, institutionalized role in the church, the state, the army or within the family as factors for choice

pronouns and rules for conversing. The two pronouns under study are Tu (T) and Vous (V). Although, the two pronouns are similar, the use of the pronoun Vous carries a mark of deference. Brown and Gilman's (1968) study which traces the evolution of the pronouns Tu and Vous argues that one person may be said to have power over another in the degree that the person is able to control the behaviour of the other. This means that power is a relationship between at least two persons and it is non-reciprocal in that both cannot have power in the same area of behaviour. According to the study, the superior says T and receives V.

Furthermore, in the solidarity semantics, the pronoun Tu is more favoured and frequently in use than the pronoun Vous. The study indicates that the younger people are moving away from the traditional norms embraced by the older people by accepting the use of the pronoun Tu. However, there are a few questions the study does not address. For example, the study does not tell us whether the French

language has pronouns for distinguishing two third persons from one another as it is the case with two second persons and what will be the nature of the rebellious attitudes of the younger generations when the older generations are finally replaced by the younger generations. The study does not say if there are occasions when the use of the pronoun Yous can reflect some other intentions apart from the factors of deference and power. In our present study of pronoun usage in the cross-cultural context, we will determine the attitudes of younger people towards the use of pronouns and also determine whether the use of plural pronouns can reflect some other intentions apart from the factor of deference.

Evans-Pritchard (1966) identifies age, sex and family relationship as factors, which show social situations among the Nilotic people of the Anglo-Egyptian Sudan. Three conclusions can be made from Evans-Pritchard's study. Any elderly male person will be addressed as father while the elderly male person will address the

unmarried male person my son. A married woman with children and unmarried girls are addressed or referred to by their personal names. Young children address everyone irrespective of age, social status and family name until they are aware of the societal norms manifested in the address system (see also Casagrande, 1966).

There are some areas which Evan-Pritchard's study does not consider and which we will consider in our present study. The study does not consider whether the elderly ones help the young children to become aware of the societal norms. But, if the elderly ones do, the elders' reactions when the young children err and if not the age at which the young children are expected to show sufficient knowledge about the societal norms. In case there is a disagreement between an elderly male person and a younger male person the study does not tell us whether the elderly male person will still be addressed as father by the younger male person and the younger male person will be addressed as son by the elderly male person.

Brown and Ford's (1966) study is also of relevance to our study of pronoun usage. The findings of the study show that there are five categories of address system in American English. The first category uses reciprocal FN (first name only). The second category uses reciprocal TLN (Title and the last name). The third category uses FN and receives TLN. The fourth category uses T (title) and receives either FN or TLN. The use of T carries more formal weight than TLN and the use shows distance between the speaker and the addressed. The fifth mode of address system is LN (last name only) and it is meant for an occasional person.

Similarly, Ervin-Tripp (1972) claims that status - marked honorifics such as Mr. Chairman, Your honour, Your Excellency, Mr. President, occupational rank differences and identity factors such as doctor and, professor can serve as modes of address in social interactions (see also Oyetade 1995). The questions that are of interest to the present study include what the sociolinguistic implications are

There are violations of these modes of address system; whether modes of address system are contingent on the presence or non-presence of the addressee and whether there are occasions when these address systems, when used, will show mockery.

Discussing language etiquette among the Javanese people, (1968) observes that choice of word or language is contingent and familiarity. Status is determined by wealth, descent, occupation, age, kinship and nationality among others. identifies three categories of language groups among the Javanese. The urbanized or slightly educated group, the peasants and uneducated townsmen and the third group use a dialect that provides a model of correct speech for the whole society. He, also, argues that the use of language consists of three approaches namely, high, middle and low and that there are two types of honorifics. They are high and low. The use of the three approaches and honorifics shows class distinction or social stratification. We can say that it is

impossible to discover occasions where the use of any of the pronouns will not reflect the speaker's or speakers' real intentions towards the addressee.

Gay and Allen's (1976) study of pronouns, proximity and the proximal other can be regarded as a continuation of Mead's (cited in Gay and Allen, 1976) analysis of the functions of pronouns. The objective of the study is to determine the frequency at which pronouns are used in social interactions. The result shows among others, that there is a strong predominance of the nominative form I and me for self-reference indicating that the self is asserted almost exclusively as initiator or emitter of action. One question which the study does not address and which we will consider in our present study is whether any sociolinguistic variables, such as power, affront, under-rating, embarrassment, fear, surprise and pride can be deduced from the use of I and me in social interactions apart from the factor of emitter of action.

Abiodun's (1992) study of pronoun usage among some Yoruba speakers shows that plural pronouns, when used, can serve as markers of power, courtesy, rebuke and humour. Abiodun (1992), also shows that the factors of presence and non-appearance of the addressee during the time of address are responsible for the choice of plural or singular pronouns.

Oyetade's (1995) sociolinguistic analysis of address forms in Yoruba shows that the standard Yoruba pronouns can be grouped into two main categories. The first category, when used, carries a mark of respect and can show either honour to second or third person singular. The second category, when used, does not carry a mark of respect and can show dishonour either to second or third person singular (see also Akindele 1990). Oyetade (1995) also argues that certain forms are occasionally used as dictated by the situational context to express transient communicative intent".

Olateju's (1997) study of pronoun usage among the Ijebu and shows that the use of singular pronouns can express anger or intimacy while the use of plural pronouns can admiration, respect and polite distance. However, while (1995) study does not tell us how we can determine the constraints in the choice of pronouns and for which purpose interactions, Abiodun's (1992) study does not tell us if there are occasions when any of the plural pronouns can be used either to or third person singular without the factors of power, rebuke and humour.

Similarly, Abiodun (1992), Oyetade (1995) and Olateju's (1997) do not address some other sociolinguistic issues such as whether there are occasions when the use of plural pronouns can serve as evidence of awareness of an action or whether there are occasions when the functions of singular and plural pronouns can indicate the meaning in social interactions. Also, the studies do not tell us

There are factors that can influence the use of any of the first singular or plural pronouns in social interactions. These areas these studies do not address will be considered in our present study of pronoun usage in social interactions.

Two conclusions can be drawn from the works already cited. First, some of the works are confirmations of the social psychologists' view that personal pronouns are indicators of social relations, social position and social function. Secondly, nouns or titles can also serve as indicators of social relations, social position and social function. In the present study of pronoun usage, we will find out if Ijesa pronouns are indicators of social relations, social function and social position.

ATTITUDES/BEHAVIOUR

Social recognition, social cooperation and social stigma are the results of choice of language, choice of word or choice of phonetic symbol. These opinions are expressed by several scholars. Hoijer's study is on the language of the Navaho Indians of New Mexico

Hoijer claims, among others, that the combination of the repetitive prefix complex with the iterative stem emphasizes and carries further denotation that such repetition is a matter of habit or custom and that such forms are particularly prominent in reports of customs and habitual modes of group

Labov (1968) discusses the reflection of social processes in linguistic structures. His concern is the social stratification of English in New York City and especially a linguistic survey of the lower east side of America. Two conclusions can be deduced from Labov's study. First, variations in pronunciation of phonological features are caused by careful conversations, formal contexts, casual contexts, pedagogic situations and social position. Secondly, two different categories of people with prestige and stigmatized forms of language choice are identifiable in a speech community (see also Labov, 1968). The difference in phonological pronunciation observed

Among the English language speakers in the study distinguishes one group from another group. We can say that if the language in question is the mother-tongue of the people then the uneducated may be better speakers but if the language is a foreign language that is imposed on people then the educated would be better speakers.

Nader's (1968) findings on the attitudes and the use of language among the Lebanese show that those who can speak an unadulterated mother-tongue are the villagers whose knowledge of their mother-tongue remains undiluted by the prestige factor which has borrowing from another language as its hallmark. However, the study does not identify the factors which make borrowing from another language an acceptable phenomenon.

Ahukanna's (1990) study of Igbo-English bilinguals' attitudes towards code-mixing behaviour becomes a noticeable issue. Ahukanna (1990) claims that earlier observers of code-mixing behaviour among Igbo-English bilinguals are of the opinion that code-mixing has assumed an

... rate and that code-mixing is a function not only of the
... of English in the Nigerian society and the multiplicity of
... of Igbo but also as a conscious display of the knowledge of
... prestigious language. The two major factors which Ahukanna
... as reasons that are responsible for code-mixing are the
... in the Igbo language to express adequately modern concepts
... science and technology and the negative attitude of Igbo
... towards their mother-tongue.

While the claim that code-mixing in Igbo is a function of the
... of English in the Nigerian society is not disputable, the
... that code-mixing is a conscious display of the knowledge
... prestigious language may not be correct. Code-mixing is not only
... occurrence among educated Nigerians, it is also a noticeable
... among the uneducated though with varying degrees. We can
... therefore say that if this is the case with the non-literate then it would
... be correct to say that those who make use of code-mixing in their

may not be showing a conscious display of the knowledge of
contiguous language.

Bourhis and Giles' (1976) findings in their study of the
of cooperation in Wales support Giles Powesland's (cited in
and Giles, 1976) claims that speech style is an important cue
an immediate impression of another person. The findings
among others, that a Welsh-speaking audience reacts more
to a plea in Welsh than in English. One conclusion we can
from the works or studies reviewed and which is of importance
present study of pronoun usage is that the positive or negative
or messages of any language or word used cannot be
unless the behaviour or attitudes of the speaker(s) are
considered. We will consider the attitudes or behaviour of our
respondents in relation to the choice of pronouns made by them so as
to determine which among the Ijesa pronouns are used for which
purpose.

SOCIOLOGY OF LANGUAGE APPROACH

The sociology of language approach represents one of several approaches to the study of the patterned co-variation of language and society (Fishman, 1968). From all known sociolinguistic studies especially in the area of language choice and language maintenance, the indispensability of sociological factors for analysing and reporting language situations of any speech community remains and not totally unquestioned. While the sociological factors of literacy help Labov (1968) to determine the variations in the phonological pronunciation among the New Yorkers in America, the sociological factors of age, sex and social status help Brown and Fishman (1968) to identify social differences in pronoun usage among French language users.

Similarly, Brown and Ford (1966) and Evans-Pritchard's (1966) studies recognise the importance of sociological factors as factors which help in reporting the true language situation in any community.

Goke-Pariola (1987) also, employs the sociology of language in his study of the sociolinguistic bases of language choice in Nigerian urban centres. The essence of the study is to determine the function of Nigerian languages and English and also the attitudes of Nigerians to the question of a national language. Having identified the functional domains of the Nigerian languages and Goke-Pariola concludes that the English language is still preferred to any of the Nigerian languages as the national language by respondents.

We can argue that if the study were carried out in another town like Ilesa or Iwo, the outcome of his study would be different from what it is. The outcome of Goke-Pariola's study could be determined because Ife is a University town where people of different ethnic and linguistic groups live and these people were essentially his respondents. Therefore, the respondents, for ethnic reasons, would prefer a neutral language like English. We are of the

the use of the sociology of language alone cannot explain the speaker's or speakers' intentions especially when the words used indicate another thing in social interactions. So, the works or studies already cited the sociology of language is for carrying out a successful investigation into this aspect study in social interactions.

Since our present study will also cover the use of pronouns in intentions, we will adopt the combination of both the of language approach and the ethnography of communication approach. While the sociology of language approach is expected to account for the variations in the use of pronouns in relation to sociological factors the ethnography of communication approach is expected to help in recognising the intentions of the Ijesa vis-a-vis the pronouns used.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

INTRODUCTION

The essence of this chapter is to highlight the methodological procedures that were employed to gather data on the Ijesa dialect. It must be recalled that the objective of this study is to investigate the aspects of choice of pronouns in relation to culture among those who speak the Ijesa dialect. This study is a descriptive study because it deals with the opinions of those who speak the Ijesa dialect. Because of the nature of this study we considered both formal and informal methods of elicitation of information.

THE FORMAL METHOD

The formal method that was adopted involved interviews with some people as well as the use of a questionnaire. The questionnaire has two parts. The first part was meant to obtain information on

personal data such as sex, age, marital status, level of education and occupation of the subjects. These parameters are important as in various ways they may constitute variables of language use.

Part two, which was divided into four sections, was designed to obtain information on choice of pronoun(s). The first section was on choice of pronoun(s) when there is no disagreement with a husband/wife, a child, parents, a married woman who is not the husband's wife, a boss, an apprentice, a person of the same status, an outsider or stranger, a person who is older, a person who is younger, a person who is of the same age, a priest or Imam, a customer, a former wife or husband, a girl or a boy friend and a rich man.

The second section sought to know which pronoun(s) would be used when there is a disagreement with a husband/wife, a child, parents, a married woman who is not one's wife, a boss, an apprentice, a person of the same status and age, an outsider or stranger, a person

older, a person who is younger, a priest or Imam, a customer, former wife husband, a girl or a boy friend and a rich person.

The third section was on choice of pronoun(s) when pronouns were used as a play on words with a husband/wife, a child, parents, a married woman who is not one's wife, a boss, an apprentice, a person of the same status and age, an outsider or stranger, a person older, a person who is younger, a priest or Imam, a customer, former wife/husband, a girl or a boy friend and a rich person.

Furthermore, the fourth section was designed to know the pronoun(s) that are used in praise - singing or derogatory remarks for husband/wife, a child, parents, a married woman who is not one's wife, a boss, an apprentice, a person of the same status, a person of the same age, a person who is older, a person who is younger, an outsider or stranger, a priest or Imam, a customer, a former wife husband, a girl of a boy friend and a rich person.

THE INFORMAL METHOD

The informal method involved audio recording of spontaneous utterances by a number of the Ijesa dialect speakers. The data collected through the informal method is the speaker's vernacular, that is, natural, unguarded usage which is the kind of data that is used for sociolinguistic investigation.

The recordings were done in public places such as restaurants and social gatherings. In all, thirty-six places were visited and the places included eight churches, three gambling houses, five markets, ten restaurants, seven motor parks, three mosques and four recreational centres. Some of the cassettes of the recordings of the Ijesa musician popularly called Adedara Arunrálójàoba were also considered and found useful as they contain unguarded usage in Ijesa dialect.

THE SAMPLING PROCEDURE

The respondents to the questionnaire were two hundred and eleven. The questionnaire forms were administered in the villages and towns. All the two hundred and eleven questionnaire copies that were given to our respondents were completed and returned. Apart from the fact that the questionnaire was designed in such a way that the respondents would not be bored, the researcher's knowledge of the area as well as the Ijesa areas was also a contributing factor to the success of the study. My assistants and I helped the uneducated respondents to record their responses in the questionnaire that was read to them.

DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

The demographic information obtained in respect of our respondents includes age, level of education, occupation, sex, marital and social statuses. This was considered very important to our present study of choice of pronouns in relation to culture in social

...tions. The importance of the demographic information is two
... The demographic information would give us an insight into the
...ground of our respondents and also help us to ascertain the
... for any variations in case there were in the respondents'
... of pronouns in relation to culture.

The respondents were divided into different age-groups using
... years as a difference between a particular age-group and another
...-group. This was in recognition of the Ijesa people's belief that the
... that are born in a period of three years belong to the same age-

There were four categories of people according to levels of
... Those who had no formal education, those who had below
... West African School Certificate (WASC), those who had the West
... School Certificate (WASC) or its equivalent and those who
... post-secondary school education. The respondents were also
...-porised into different occupational levels. They were farmers,

civil servants, artisans, students and those looking for employment. It was assumed that age, level of education and social status would help in determining the attitudes and preferences of people towards choice of pronouns in social interactions.

THE HYPOTHESES

In relation to the questions that were posed in the formal part of our investigation as well as in the recording of informal conversations, we had the following hypotheses:

- Ho¹ Elderly people use singular pronouns in addressing the younger people, the younger people use plural pronouns for the elderly people.
- Ho² A boss would adopt singular pronouns as modes of address to an apprentice, the apprentice would adopt plural pronouns as modes of address to his boss.
- Ho³ The use of singular pronouns reciprocally obtains between people of the same status or age.

- Ho⁶ Sisters or brothers-in-law are addressed with plural pronouns by brothers' wives; brothers' wives are addressed with singular pronouns by sisters or brothers-in-law.
- Ho⁷ Between sellers and buyers and between a person and a stranger, reciprocal use of plural pronouns obtains.
- Ho⁷ Parents adopt singular pronouns as modes of address to their children; on the other hand, children adopt plural pronouns as modes of address to their parents.
- Ho⁷ Between husbands and wives, reciprocal use of singular pronouns is the case.
- Ho⁸ The rich usually receive plural pronouns from the poor, but the poor would be addressed with singular pronouns by the rich.

Visitors adopt singular pronouns as modes of address to children; in turn, children adopt plural pronouns as modes of address to visitors.

There are reasons for postulating these hypotheses. Hypotheses 8 and 9 were based on the fact that differences in age and social status can be responsible for variations in the choice of pronouns (see Geertz 1966, Abiodun 1992). The reason for the third and seventh hypotheses was the assumption that familiarity, as people say, breeds contempt and singular pronouns, when used, are indicators of familiarity in some cases (see Olateju 1997).

Furthermore, the fifth hypothesis was motivated by the claim that unfamiliarity requires respect and plural pronouns, when used, indicate respect (see Oyetade 1995). The fourth hypothesis was based on the assumption that in the Yoruba traditional society wives are expected to show deference in their interactions with either sisters' or

brothers-in-law although the reverse may be the case from either
brothers-in-law to the wives (see Adeoye 1979).

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

Although, Abiodun's (1992) study examines pronoun usage in
the study can be said to be done in passing. This is because the
which Abiodun (1992) gives in support of deference in
system in Ijesa are taken from some Yoruba literature books
translated to Ijesa (see Fagunwa 1950:49, Isola 1970:8, Yemitan
and Akinola 1984:88). The present sociolinguistic study of
pronouns in the socio-cultural context will be a more
comprehensive sociolinguistic study of pronoun usage among the
people. It is hoped that the findings of the present study will
enrich our sociolinguistic knowledge of pronoun usage in
interactions.

CHAPTER FOUR

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

INTRODUCTION

In this chapter, we will like to analyse the results of the interviews and the recorded utterances in relation to the hypotheses that were previously postulated. The study is descriptive because it deals with the opinions of the people that speak the Ijesa dialect. It should be recalled that the information that will form the focus of this chapter was collected through the use of a questionnaire as well as through tape recorded utterances in the informal setting. For easy access, the subjects' responses and the recorded utterances are organised into twelve sections.

PRONOUN CHOICE BETWEEN OLDER AND YOUNGER PEOPLE

The questionnaire was designed to find out the pronouns that were adopted in addressing either an elderly person or a younger person when there is no disagreement, when there is a disagreement, or simply as a play on words or during praise -singing. Hypothesis 1 is the focus here, i.e, Elderly people use singular pronouns in addressing the younger people, the younger people use plural pronouns for the elderly people.

The findings are as follows:

The choice of pronouns made by some people, in some cases especially when there is no disagreement, may show differences in social division, distance, status and education. The younger ones address the older ones with plural pronouns and the older ones use singular pronouns for the younger ones.

Younger: Ìn-in ni mée kí

(Is you (plural) I am greeting).

Older: Bẹẹ ni tẹ rí. Ọ káre

(You (singular) always do so. You (singular) have done well)

Older: Mé rí ọ lánàá

(I did not see you (singular) yesterday).

Younger: Mé rí ìn-in nàá

(I also did not see you (plural) too).

Younger: Mée kí ìn-in lánàá lójà

(I was greeting you (plural) yesterday at the market)

Older: Ọ wà lójà? Mé rí ọ

(You (singular) were in the market? I did not see you (singular))

Older: Uṣé rẹ̀ ikó?

(How is your (singular) work?)

Younger: Éé lọ. In ṣe

(It is going. Thank you (plural))

The factor of age may also be responsible for the reciprocal use of plural pronouns in some cases. A person of higher status may use plural pronouns for a person of lower status, if the person of lower status is an elderly person. Although, in addition to the factor of age, the factor of literacy or education may serve as the basis of the reciprocal use of plural pronouns between the speaker and the addressee.

Furthermore, domain or context does affect pronoun usage in social interactions. Singular pronouns are usually in use in a place where games are played when people must have returned from their farms or places of work.

Ó ta?

(Will you (singular) not play?)

Ó yé pa mí ni?

(Can you (singular) defeat me?)

Ọn-ọn pè ó. Éẹ̀ sùwọ̀ jẹ̀ bàbáa Sádé?

(They are calling you (singular). Are you (singular) not Sade's father?)

Gbọ́ọ̀ rẹ̀

(Remove your (singular) hand)

in the domain of *ayò* game, equality, intimacy and friendliness

to replace the factors of social status, education and age in

singular pronouns as modes of address. The adoption of

pronouns, irrespective of the difference in sociological

at places where games are played is not limited to the *Ijesa*

speakers alone; it is also the case among other Yoruba groups

other Yoruba dialects.

Again, the factor of topic may be responsible for the adoption of singular pronouns as a mode of address from a younger person to an older person. For example, songs, praise-songs and eulogies are often about happenings or phenomena in the Ijesa socio-cultural lives. In these cases, Ijesa singular pronouns play significant roles and it is not the case when singers, praise singers and those who are at work in eulogies are at work. In other words, as our data reveal, it can be argued that the use of Ijesa singular pronouns in songs, praise-songs and eulogies is one of the instances one can cite against the claim that singular pronouns are, in all cases, pronouns of disrespect and discourtesy when used in social interactions.

The adoption or use of singular pronouns in praising people is a cultural practice which is not peculiar to the Ijesa people alone; it is a cultural phenomenon among those who speak the standard Yoruba as well as speakers of the other Yoruba dialects. For example,

Owá ni mǎá fóní kí o

Arómọ́lǎran àrólé

Owá ni mǎá fóní kí o

Arómọ́lẹ́rẹ́n ẹ́rọ́lẹ́

Ọ́ tutù bí ọ̀sùn

Ọwá arọ́jò joyè

Ọ́ dẹnú ilé tejiteji

Dékúnlé ọ

Ìyèrẹ ọ́kín yọ lọ́jà

Ọ́ bá bábá rẹ jọ

Arúbùtu rúbùtu

Ọ́ tutù lẹwà

Ọ́ bọmọ sùn kẹwà ranmọ

Ọmọ orí ẹ̀bẹ̀joyè

Ọmọ gbégbá ajé

Ìlẹ ọmọ bẹpo lẹwà ọkúnrin

Arómọ́lẹ́rẹ́n ẹ́rọ́lẹ́

Ọ̀sùpá ilẹ̀kí a mọ roro lágbo

Ọ́ pọ́n lẹ̀sẹ bí ẹ̀lẹ́rẹ́

Dekunleee

Ua darigbó olójà

Ua dèè dàgbà oyè

Gbogbo ara laalágedu fii rirú

Yá wò ó

Yá wò ó

Arábà lilà ee líjèsà

E şe mo dúpé

Ọwá ni màá fóní kí

Dekunleee

Yèye re ló bí o silè

Kí bàbá tó mò o lomọ

Unun oni şe léé yèni

Dékúnlé yèé ye o o

Unun oni şe léé yèni

Omọ egbèrin èbù

Omọ egbèrin ùporo

Unun oni şe léé yèni

Aromolaran yèé yè ó o

Èmi Arúnunràlòjàoba

Lò mi kée sí o

Romolaran, mọ yò í o

Romolaran, mọ yò í bàba rẹ

Dekunle, màá bọ dádúgbò rẹ

Translation

I will use today to praise Owá

Aromolaran, the pillar of the house

I will praise Owá for the whole of today.

Aromolaran, the pillar of the house

He (singular) who is fresh like a vegetable

Owá, who takes up chieftaincy title amidst rainfall

He (singular) who enters the house soaked

with rainwater

Dekunle o!

The pea-cock arrives at the market

It is identical with your (singular)

father

Round and robust

He (singular), who is fresh with beauty

He (singular) who transfers beauty to

a lady during sexual intercourse.

He, whose head is persuaded to take

up a chieftaincy title

An industrious child

Welldone, a man whose handsomeness

gushes out palm oil from its container

Aromolaran, the pillar of the house

The glorious moon that brightly glows

amidst the circle of people

Your (singular) legs are fairly
complexioned like "àláári".

Dekunleee

You (singular) will live to grow old like the "olójà"

You (singular) will equally live and grow old
on your (singular) chieftaincy title.

"Alagedu" tree bountifully brings forth "in" seed.

Call and have a look!

Come and have a look!

The great "Araba" in Ijesaland

Thanks. I am grateful

I shall use today to praise "Owá"

Dekunleee

Your (singular) mother was the first to bring

you (singular) into existence

Before your (singular) father stamps

your (singular) existence.

One is glorified by what one
personally does.

Dékúnlé, this glorifies you (singular)

One is glorified by what one personally does.

The child of eight hundred yam seeds

The child of eight hundred heap spaces

One is glorified by what one personally does.

Aromọ́lاران, this glorifies you (singular)

I, Arúnunrálójàọ́ba

Am exhorting you (singular)

Romọ́lاران, I rejoice with you (singular)

Romọ́lاران, I rejoice with your (singular) father

Dékúnlé, I shall accompany you (singular)

to your area of domain.

The recorded utterances and our subjects' responses to the ~~utterance~~ show that singular pronouns are used as modes of ~~usage~~ in songs, praise-songs and eulogies irrespective of the ~~speaker's~~ age, level of education and social status in the society.

As the topic changes pronoun usage may also change. In some ~~cases~~ there may be reciprocal use of plural pronouns between an ~~older~~ person and a younger person. Such usage may be evidence of a ~~relationship~~ in words. Under this condition deference is not intended.

Older: Áá ki in-in

(We (instead of I) are greeting you (plural))

Younger: Ìa náà dáhùn

(We (instead of I) too, are answering)

Four deductions can be made from the reciprocal use of the ~~plural~~ pronouns. First, it is possible for any of the first person plural ~~pronouns~~ to be adopted by a single person in social interactions. ~~Second~~, the use of plural pronouns in social interactions can show

Similarly, depending on the subject of discussion, the use of the second person plural pronoun may indicate disdain or a question. For

Younger: *Yèsí ọ̀n yàń gégé bí alága?*

(Who did they appoint as the chairman?)

Elder: *Èmi*

(I)

Younger: *Ìn-in?*

(You (plural)?)

If the second person plural pronoun indicates disdain then the pronoun is used because the addressee is physically present. It shows that there is a strained relationship between the speaker and the addressee. Reasons for choice of a pronoun or pronouns as an indicator or indicators of disdain are bad behaviour, disagreement, and lack of credibility.

Again, depending on the tone, the first person pronoun qualifier is used by a person to ask a question or to express an affront, indignation and surprise in social interactions. For example,

Younger: Tin-in

(Your (plural) own)

Older: Tèmi?

(My (singular) own?)

In another context, the use of the first person pronoun qualifier may signify greed, satisfaction or refusal. However, the addressee's response will further help in determining the interpretation of the use of the first person pronoun qualifier.

A younger person: Tin-in

(Your (plural) own)

An older person: Tèmi?

(My (singular) own?)

There are occasions when an older person can adopt plural pronouns as a mode of address for a younger person in social situations.

Older: Ó yá in

(You (plural) have come in time)

Younger: Mé tètè rókò

(I did not see a vehicle early enough)

Older: Ìn jí a ríra tín-in bá se tán

(You (plural) should give me attention when you (plural) are through with what you are doing)

The use of plural pronouns in this context does not carry the factor of deference but that the speaker frowns at the addressee's behaviour in coming late.

Furthermore, death can serve as an occasion for the use of Ijesa singular pronouns. When death occurs the deceased in most cases is addressed with singular pronouns. Under this condition, the deceased

...older or younger and the speaker(s) may be older or younger.

...example,

A: Sọ gbọ pé bábá Fẹmi kú?

(Did you hear that Fẹmi's father died?)

B: Ó kú?

(He (singular) died?)

A: Ó kú

(He (singular) died)

B: Sọ dàgbà?

(Was he (singular) so old?)

A: Ó fẹ̀ tógórin

(He (singular) was almost eighty)

B: Ó dàgbà. Yèni náà tó.

(He (singular) was old. That is enough)

Similarly, non-appearance can be a factor for the use of Ijesa singular pronouns in social interactions. When the addressee is not physically present during the time of address, singular pronouns are,

... adopted as modes of address for the addressee. The age
... position of the addressee may not count.

Two Friends

A: Kàri ọ̀ọ̀ tii ọ̀ọ̀?

(Where are you (singular) coming from?)

B: Mọ̀ tàòfin-in ọ̀ọ̀

(I am coming from the palace)

A: Kábièsí ikó?

(How is Kábièsí or the King?)

B: Ó wà lúbẹ̀

(He (singular) is there)

Between Two Students

A: N gbọ̀ ọ̀ lọ sí sùkùrù lóníí?

(Excuse me, did you go to school today?)

B: Mọ̀ lọ

(I went)

☛ *Se tisa Biology wa?*

(Did biology teacher come?)

☛ *O wa*

(He/she (singular) came)

☛ *O wa?*

(He/she (singular) came?)

☛ *Maa puru? O wa sugin e pe*

(Will I be lying? He/she (singular) came but he/she (singular) did not stay long).

If the king or the teacher were physically present during the address, neither the king nor the teacher would have been addressed with singular pronouns.

In sermons, Ijesa singular pronouns are usually adopted as address either from an older person to a younger person or from a younger person to an older person. The sermon message could be Islamic or Christian. For example,

Islamic Preaching in the Mosque

Imam: Olórun í káa tójú iyáò ríá. Úwọ tóo fiyáò
ilẹ tóo tójú tóo ẹ dáadáá lóde, ẹsin rẹ pé

(God said we should take care of our wives. You (singular) who (singular) have left your wife uncared for and you (singular) are doing well outside, your (singular) religion is not complete).

Christian Preaching in the Church

Rev: Kónikàn bámi sí úwé Eksodu ori ogún ẹsẹ ikẹta sí
ikésàn-án kẹẹ kà á.

(Let somebody help me open the book of Exodus chapter 20:3-9 and he/she (singular) should read).

Reader: Íwọ kò gbọdọ ní Olórun miirán pẹlú mi.

(You must not have any other god with me)

Rev: Ó gbọdọ lólórun miirán pẹlú rẹ.

(You (singular) must not have any other god with him)

Reader: *Ìwọ kò gbòdò yá èrekére fún ara re*
 (You must not make for yourself a carved image)

Rev: *Ó gbòdò yérekére fàrà re*
 (You (singular) must not make a carved image for
 yourself (singular))

Reader: *Ìwọ kò gbòdò pe orúko Olórun re lásán.*
 (You must not call the name of your God in vain)

Rev: *Ó gbòdò porúko Olórun re lásán.*
 (You (singular) must not call the name of your
 (singular) God in vain).

Although, singular pronouns are used where many people are present, the preacher expects the message to be individualised irrespective of the person's age, education and social status. Our findings, in this section on pronoun exchange between older and younger persons suggest we reject the hypothesis that elderly people use singular pronouns in addressing the younger people and the younger people use plural pronouns in addressing the elderly people.

PRONOUN CHOICE BETWEEN A BOSS AND AN APPRENTICE

The questionnaire sought to know the pronouns that were adopted as modes of address between a boss and an apprentice. The second hypothesis is that a boss would adopt singular pronouns as modes of address to an apprentice, the apprentice would adopt plural pronouns as modes of address to his boss. The responses of the subjects as well as the recorded utterances are presented below.

In some cases, the differences in age, interactions and intimacy are usually responsible for the differences in pronoun exchange between a boss and an apprentice. A boss uses singular pronouns and an apprentice uses plural pronouns while an apprentice uses plural pronouns and a boss uses singular pronouns.

Apprentice: *Sé kimi lá rí in-in?*

(Do I come to see you (plural)?)

Boss: Sémi?

(I?)

Apprentice: Ìn-in

(You (plural))

Apprentice: Onikàn lá bèèrè rin-in lànàá

(Somebody came to ask of you (plural)

yesterday)

Boss: O seun

(Thank you (singular))

in some cases, lack of exposure or education may be

responsible for an apprentice's use of singular pronouns for a boss.

example

Boss: Sòò sèsè débi usé ni?

(Have you (singular) just arrived at the place
of work?)

Apprentice: Urò o. Ulé Şadé lọ wá lúgbù mo dé.

(Not at all. You (singular) were at Şadé's house when I came)

Apprentice: Olúşẹẹ wá lánáá lúgbọ jáde.

(The owner of this work came yesterday when you (singular) went out)

Boss: Ó wí ọn wí uşẹ ti pari?

(Did you (singular) not tell him or her that the work is ready?)

Apprentice: Mo wí bẹẹ

(I said so)

Boss: É moó kò ó?

(Did he/she not give you (singular) money)

Apprentice: Urò

(Not at all)

It is either the addressee is indifferent to the choice of singular pronouns by the apprentice or that the apprentice is judged 'local' by

addressee. This mode of address is also common among the Ekiti speakers. However, in the Oyo-speaking area, language use or exchange is different. Pronouns that have deference are employed by an apprentice as modes of address for a boss.

In some cases, a boss can adopt the use of plural pronouns for apprentice:

Boss: Tin-in bá ri kin-in jé a ri
 (If you (plural) see it you (plural) should allow us to see it)

Apprentice: Mèé wa
 (I am looking for it)

Boss: Ìn-á ri
 (You (plural) will see it)

The inference that can be drawn from the choice of plural pronouns for the apprentice is that the apprentice must have been handling things at the work-shop. In this example therefore, plural

pronouns are not employed to show deference to the apprentice; they are used to show carelessness and lack of responsibility on the part of the apprentice.

Furthermore, some of the Ijesa pronouns can serve as indicators of deference. In this case, plural pronouns are usually in use and the singular does not carry deference. A boss receives plural pronouns and uses singular pronouns. An apprentice uses plural pronouns and receives plural pronouns.

- Boss: *Ìn sùsé dèmi*
 (You (plural) should work before I come)
- Apprentice: *Úpàdé rìn-ìn ikó?*
 (How is your (plural) meeting)

When a person is addressed with a plural pronoun under this condition, it is assumed that the addressee is representing a person or more than one person. So, the use of the plural pronouns is not only for the addressee that is physically present but also for the represented

are not physically present during the time of address. In
 the use of plural pronouns is reciprocal in this case
 the factor of deference.

Through the use of either third person singular or plural
 either a boss or an apprentice can be discussed. For

A. Maa fẹmọ ọn

(I will marry this girl)

B. Yẹsì?

(Who?)

C. Yéé gbẹbáá ulé rẹ

(The one living beside your (singular) house)

D. Iyáó ọgá mọ ni

(She is Master's wife)

E. Tin-ọn!

(His (plural) own!)

The third person plural pronoun used in this conversation was used for the boss and there are some deductions that can be made from the use of the third person plural pronoun. First, it may mean that the boss does not need to marry another wife since he has got a wife. Secondly, it may mean that the apprentice does not actually know that the lady is his boss's wife. The speaker may know another person with the girl as her fiance. The speaker does not consider it desirable for the boss to have such a girl as a wife. The expression of fear can also be deduced from the use of the third person plural pronoun.

Again, the third person plural pronoun used as a mode of address for a boss could serve as an indicator of threat. For example,

A: *Ògá pè ó*

(The master is calling you (singular))

B: *Yèsí?*

(Who?)

A: Ìn-ọ̀n mà ni
(He (plural) is the one)

B: Ùgbẹ̀ẹ̀ ikó
(Therefore)

A: Ìn-ọ̀n!
(He (plural) !)

Similarly, the use of the third person plural pronoun in the conversation below may serve as either an indicator of shame or

Apprentice A: Ọ̀ gbóhun tó selẹ̀?
(Did you (singular) not hear what happened?)

Apprentice B: Mẹ̀ gbọ̀
(I did not hear)

Apprentice A: Ọ̀gá fọ̀mọ̀ kàn lóyún
(The master impregnated a child)

Apprentice B: Ìn-òn

(He (plural))

Apprentice B: Ìyàó rin-òn ikó?

(What about his (plural) wife?)

Apprentice A: Ọn wà

(She (plural) is)

Bad behaviour, harshness and lack of credibility may be responsible for the choice of the third person singular pronoun in the conversation below.

A: Ọgá ikó?

(Where is the master?)

B: Èwo?

(Which one?)

A: Ọga re

(Your (singular) own)

B *Ó lãa gbápótí ibò*

(He (singular) went to contest for an election)

A *Óun?*

(He (singular)?)

The choice of the third person singular pronoun may also mean the boss will not win the election he has gone to participate in. We can also say from our findings that our hypothesis that bosses must adopt singular pronouns as modes of address for apprentices and apprentices would adopt plural pronouns as modes of address for bosses is not always strictly observed.

PRONOUN CHOICE BETWEEN BOYS AND GIRLS

One of the questions which our respondents were asked to respond to was whether plural or singular pronouns would be adopted as modes of address for a boy friend or girl friend. Our hypothesis that the use of singular pronouns would be the case between a boy friend and a girl friend must be rejected. This is because the topic of

Person determines choice of pronouns and these pronouns could be singular or plural.

For example, because of the similarity in age, the adoption of singular pronouns, in most cases, is usually the case between a boy and a girl. In some cases such singular pronouns may serve as a sign of friendliness, intimacy, contemporariness and equality. For example,

Boy: Mọ wá ọ délé mẹ bá ọ

(I came to look for you (singular) at home, I did not meet you (singular))

Girl: Mọ jáde. Ọ tíjọ méta

(I went out. Quite an age)

Boy: Ọhun náà ni mo ọ wí kímí wò ọ lúlé.

(That was why I came to look for you (singular) at home)

Girl: O ṣeun. Èmi náà rò wí ó yẹ kímí tí dódò rẹ.

(Thank you (singular). I, too, thought it was necessary I should check you (singular) at home)

The factor of topic may however make the use of singular pronouns, pronouns of pride, disdain, surprise and refusal. For example,

Boy: Kàrí ọ

(You (singular), come)

Girl: Èmi rée

(Here I am)

Boy: Mǎá fẹ ọ

(I will marry you (singular))

Girl: Úwọ?

(You (singular)?)

Pride, disdain, surprise and refusal may be based on education, social status, family background and differences in ethnic

stability. For example, there is a claim among the Ijesa people which is known as 'Yèsá a fòyòò?' (who will marry an Oyo man?).

Furthermore, while plural pronouns are used as a play on words in addressing each other, singular or plural pronouns could be used for each other to express disaffection or disagreement.

4.4 PRONOUN CHOICE BETWEEN PEOPLE OF THE SAME AGE OR STATUS

In the questionnaire we wanted to know the pronouns that are used between people of the same status or age for various purposes. Our hypothesis is the use of singular pronouns reciprocally obtains between people of the same status or age. Our findings, show that both singular and plural pronouns are usually adopted as modes of address for each other or for one another among people who are of the same age or status. However, reasons for the adoption of singular or plural pronouns vary. For example,

A: Uṣu mélòó o gbìn?

(How many yams did you (singular) plant?)

B: Mọ gbìn ẹgbèrún

(I planted one thousand)

B: Tiẹ íkò?

A: É ju ẹ̀dẹ̀gbèrín

(It is not more than seven hundred)

A: Àbí mọ rí si lòdò rẹ?

(Can I get more from you (singular)?)

B: Mẹẹ wá

(I am still looking for more)

A: Tiẹ ju tèmi lọ

(Your (singular) own is more than my own)

B: Àgbẹ oníkòkò lọ rẹ

(You (singular) are a cocoa farmer)

A: Ọ ṣeun.

(Thank you (singular))

In this conversation, *occupation, familiarity and intimacy* are responsible for the use of pronouns of disrespect.

In another occasion, context, attitudes and physical strength serve as bases of pronouns of disrespect. For example,

A: *Úwòyí ọdún ẹẹ bọ màá pọgóta ọdún*

(This time next year, I will be sixty years old)

B: *Èmi náà ikó?*

(What about myself?)

A: *Àgbà pẹ kànniyàn*

(It does not take time for people to get old)

B: *Àwọn ọmọ sì wà lúlé ùwé*

(Children are still in the school)

A: *Tí mọ bá rọmọbinrin kékeré kan màá sì fẹ*

(If I see a small girl, I will still marry her)

B: *Úwọ*

(You (singular))

The use of the second person singular pronoun may signify disapproval or unseriousness because of the addressee's behaviour which does not consider the old age and the financial implications.

Furthermore, for a play on words, reciprocal use of plural pronouns is usually the case. But, for a disagreement, modes of address could either be plural or singular pronouns depending on the pronoun the initiator of the address uses. The findings have therefore shown that the hypothesis that the use of singular pronouns would be the case between people of the same status or age should be rejected.

PRONOUN CHOICE BETWEEN BROTHERS OR SISTERS-IN-LAW AND BROTHERS' WIVES

In the questionnaire we asked our respondents which pronouns they adopt in addressing sisters or brothers-in-law and brothers' wives. The hypothesis is sisters or brothers-in-law are addressed with plural

means by brothers' wives, brothers' wives are addressed with singular pronouns by sisters or brothers-in-law.

Choice of pronouns is contingent on illiteracy and literacy. Among the illiterate group, familiarity is usually responsible for the use of singular pronouns as modes of address between a brother's wife and a brother's wife. The wife uses singular pronouns for those who are her husband's relatives especially if she is older than them and receives singular pronouns from them.

- | | |
|---------------------|--|
| Wife: | Yá bámi gbe
(You (singular) come and help me carry it) |
| Husband's relative: | Ó ye gbe?
(You (singular) can not carry it?). |
| Wife: | Màá yé gbe kimi pè <u>ó</u>
(If I could carry it, would I call you (singular)?) |

Among the literate group, reciprocal use of plural pronouns remains in most cases especially if the sisters or brothers-in-law have attained the age of maturity.

Wife: *Antí in yá wo unun mọ rà*
 (Auntie you (plural) should come and look at what
 I bought).

Sister: *Ó dára. In mọjà níná*
 (It is good. You (plural) are good at bargaining
 wares).

However, in *ljesa* as well as in any of the Yoruba traditions, there are also ways through which either an educated or an uneducated wife shows deference to any of her husband's relatives. Some of the names like 'akòwé' (student), 'bùròdá' (brother), 'eyinafé' (somebody with bright teeth) can be adopted for a boy while 'ibádi' (the buttock of a good cloth), 'àntí' (auntie) can be adopted for a girl. The wife can also adopt any name either for a boy or for a girl

... as the name adopted as a mode of address is not the relative's
... or real name.

Furthermore, depending on the context or topic, a wife's use of
the first person singular pronoun on an issue that has to do with the
... of her husband may mean pride, refusal or affront. For
example,

Husband: Bami fọso àbúrò mi ni

(Help me wash that my brother's cloth)

Wife: Èmi?

(I?)

Assigning work to a wife by her husband is based on the fact
that in Ijesa as well as in any of the Yoruba culture, a wife is seen as
a "slave". So, it is the wife's responsibility to serve every person born
... she became a wife in the house. The wife's reaction may also
reflect a conflict between the wife and the husband's relative. The
... thesis that sisters or brothers-in-law would be addressed with

plural pronouns by brothers' wives and brothers' wives would be addressed with singular pronouns by sisters or brothers-in-law is hereby rejected. The rejection is based on the fact that it is not in all cases that sisters or brothers-in-law are addressed with plural pronouns and it is not in all cases that brothers' wives are addressed with singular pronouns.

4.6 PRONOUN CHOICE BETWEEN SELLERS AND BUYERS

The hypothesis is between sellers and buyers, reciprocal use of plural pronouns obtains. Our findings on the questions that were put to our respondents on the pronouns they would use in addressing a seller or a buyer show the following; In some cases, first person pronoun qualifier and plural pronouns are used as modes of address in the business domain. For example,

Seller: Okò mi, wugbá

(My husband, look at the shop)

- Seller: Ìn túbò wò ó
(You (plural) should look at it very well or again)
- Buyer: Ìn kù ọrò ajé. Sájé ọ gbá?
(You (plural) are greeted for the ups and downs that go with business. Are there sales?)
- Seller: A dúpé. Ìn báa wugbá
(We (instead of I) are grateful, You (plural) should patronise us)
- Buyer: Èlò ìn-ìn ta yèé
(How much are you (plural) selling this?)
- Seller: Pónùn méjọ. Ìn mú tin-ìn ní méje àbò
(Eight pounds. You (plural) should take your (plural) own at the rate of seven pounds, ten shillings)

Buyer: Ó họn yéye. Ìn bámi òm níbẹ̀
 (It is too costly. You (plural) should reduce the price for me)

Seller: É gbà. Ìn fẹ́ náó. Ìn-ìn ó ẹ̀ ni, mée turú rẹ̀.
 (It is not acceptable. You (plural) do not want to spend money. It is because you (plural) are the one, I do not sell like that)

While patronage, economic gain and marketing strategy are the factors which a seller employs in choosing the first person pronoun qualifier if the seller is a woman and plural pronouns for a buyer, age, education and newness influence a buyer's decision in adopting either singular or plural pronouns for a seller. The use of first person pronoun qualifier 'mi' (my) by the seller for the buyer is an indication of extreme politeness and the essence is to lure or encourage the buyer to patronize her.

Similarly, poor negotiations or pricing may lead to the reciprocal use of plural pronouns essentially to show mockery and annoyance. The seller initiates the use of plural pronouns and receives plural pronouns. But if the buyer is very young then the seller might adopt singular pronouns in addressing the buyer. Though, the buyer may make use of plural or singular pronouns for the seller.

Seller: *Ìn móó rè á, mo kúkú ji ni*

(You (plural) should bring the money after all I stole the goods).

Buyer: *Ìn mó binú. Şújà ni?*

(You (plural) should not be annoyed. Is it a fight?).

The adoption of a plural pronoun or a singular pronoun by the seller shows lack of good marketing strategy on the part of the seller. The seller's attitude or behaviour is a cultural phenomenon that is common among all the Yoruba ethnic groups. Whereas, this is not the

case among the Igbo and the Hausa people. Again, our hypothesis is rejected in view of the findings.

4.7 PRONOUN CHOICE BETWEEN A PERSON AND A STRANGER

The research hypothesis was that reciprocal use of plural pronouns between a person and a stranger obtains. However, some of the findings show that age, unfamiliarity and mistaken identity can serve as bases for pronoun usage between a person and a stranger. Reciprocal use of plural pronouns as a mark of deference will be the case if both the stranger and the person are adults. For example,

A stranger: Ìn pèlè lúbeé

(You (plural) are greeted here)

A person: Ìn pèlè. Yèsi in-in bèèrè?

(You (plural) are greeted. Who are you (plural) looking for)

A stranger: Mèé bèèrè olùléé

(I am looking for the owner of this house)

A person: Mè rà rójú rin-in rí

(I have never seen your (plural) face before)

A stranger: Àlejò ni mè rè

(I am a stranger)

A person: Àlejò ni in rè?

(You (plural) are a stranger?)

But, if the stranger and the person are not adults, reciprocal use of singular pronouns between the two would be the case. For example,

A stranger: In pèlé lúléé

(Greetings to you in this house)

A person: Yèsí óó bèèrè?

(Who are you (singular) looking for?)

A stranger: Mèé béèrè bàbá rè

(I am asking for your (singular) father)

Also, if the stranger is an adult and the person is not an adult, the stranger would adopt singular pronouns in addressing the person while the person might adopt plural pronouns in addressing the stranger especially if the person is above the age of five years. For example,

A stranger: Ìn pèlè lùléé

(Greetings to you in this house)

A person: Yésì in-in béèrè?

(Who are you (plural) looking for?)

A stranger: Mèé béèrè bàbá rè

(I am asking for your (singular) father)

Mistaken identity can be responsible for the use of either singular or plural pronouns for the addressee. For example,

A stranger: Ìn pèlè lùbéé

(Greeting to you (plural) here)

A person: Ìn pẹ̀lẹ̀

(Greeting to you (plural))

A stranger: Ó tíjọ́ mẹ́ta

(It has been a long time)

A person: Ijọ́ kan pẹ̀lú. Ìn pẹ̀lẹ̀

(Another day is added. You (plural) are greeted)

A stranger: Ìn mò mí mò?

(You (plural) do not recognise me any longer)

A person: Mè rà mò ín. Şin-ín binú?

(I do not recognise you (plural). I hope you (plural) are not annoyed?)

A stranger: Èmi ọmọ Şadé tée gbékòò

(I am Sade's son who lives in Lagos)

A person: Uwọ ní. Ọ̀tò lẹ̀ni mo pè é. Ọ káre.

(It is you (singular). I have mistaken you (singular) for another person. Good of you (singular)).

It can also be the other way depending on the person that is involved. Our findings show that the research hypothesis should be rejected.

4.8 PRONOUN CHOICE BETWEEN PARENTS AND CHILDREN

The hypothesis which we postulated for pronoun usage between parents and children was that parents adopt singular pronouns as modes of address to their children on the other hand, children adopt plural pronouns as modes of address to their parents. Our findings would show that this hypothesis might not be valid because there are differences in pronoun usage between parents and children who are educated and those who are not educated.

Among the illiterate parents and children, a child who is old can address his or her parents with singular pronouns and he or she can be addressed with singular pronouns. In other words, pronouns of familiarity are commonly used as modes of address. For example,

Wife: Úwọ ni kọọ yá gbérú mí

(You (singular) are the one to come and help put the load on me)

Husband: Ó ye gbe?

(You (singular) can not carry it?)

Wife: Mé ye gbe. Ó mò wí ó pò

(I can not carry it, Don't you (singular) know that it is much).

Son: Bàa mí, ó şşş tokoo bọ látóúrò

(My father you (singular) are just coming from the farm since morning).

Father: Íyáo rẹ íkó?

(How is your (singular) wife?)

Mother: Ó sọ fun wí ó tójó méta?

(Did you (singular) tell her that it has been a long time?)

Son: Ó ri, ó yá wo

(You (singular) did not see her, you (singular) did not come and see her).

Choice of singular pronouns as modes of address is not limited to the Ijesa people alone it is also the case among Ekiti, Ondo and Ife. However, among the illiterate couples and children in the Oyo-speaking area, the use of singular pronouns is not common. There are instances where children who are below five years of age call their mothers names but they desist from doing so when they are aware of the societal norms present in the address system or when they are corrected by the elderly ones.

Furthermore, in the course of a conversation, switching from singular pronouns to plural pronouns by a speaker is possible. When this is the case, annoyance and disappointment are envisaged. For example,

Father/Mother: *Ọn jùsé mi fún ọ?*

(Did he/she (plural) not deliver my message to you?)

Son/Daughter: *Ọn jùsé. Oó mề wá fòmò mi tára rẹ yá si wà nibè.*

(He/she (plural) delivered the message. I am still looking for money for my child that is sick).

Father/Mother: *Ìn pèlé, ìn kú ùnáo*

(Greeting to you (plural) and, you (plural) are also greeted for the money spent)

Son/Daughter: *Ìn sẹ*

(Thank you (plural)).

The father's or mother's use of pronouns of deference in this context shows annoyance and disappointment at non-fulfilment of the financial obligations or help required from the son or daughter to the

mother or to the father. The use of a pronoun of deference by the son or daughter is also an indication that he or she cannot do what he or she does not have the financial power to do.

Switching from singular pronouns to plural pronouns is also common with any other group especially when there is a disagreement. For example,

Wife: Oó ijẹ omò rẹ?

(Where is money for your (singular) child's food?)

Husband: Á ti gboó úwọ náà bójú tó yẹe ni.

(We have not collected money or salary, you (singular) should take care of that).

Wife: In kúusé rin-in

(You (plural) are greeted for your (plural) work)

Husband: In şeun

(Thank you (plural)).

Again, parents use singular pronouns for their children when the children are still under their control and the parents in most cases, then receive plural pronouns from their children.

Child: Baa mi, in móó ijijẹ mi kòmí

(My father, you (plural) should give me money for my food)

Father: Oó ẹ rèé

(This is your (singular) money)

Child: Yèe mi in wíjijẹ dẹmí mée re sùkùrù

(My mother, you (plural) should prepare food in readiness for me. I am going to the school).

Mother: Maa wa dẹ ò, ọ káre.

(I will get it ready for you (singular) good of you (singular).

Child: Yè mi, kàri jíjẹ ọ wá dèmi

(My mother where is the food you (singular) prepared for me?).

Mother: Ijije re rée

(This is your (singular) food).

Our findings show that while deference in pronoun usage from a child to his father is a result of less interactions between fathers and children, greater intimacy and affection are responsible for familiar usage in pronoun usage from children to mothers.

However, there are occasions when mothers can use plural pronouns for children who are adults. For example,

Child: Áá yẹ kara ọ̀n náà ti yá

(By now you should be alright)

Mother: Ọ yá. In ẹun. Ọmọ á tójú in-in náà

(I am alright. Thank you (plural). Children will take care of you (plural)).

Plural pronouns that are used in this context show deference and are used in recognition of the son's or daughter's wealth and assistance to the mother. In addition to the honorific use of plural pronouns as modes of address for children who are wealthy adults, some mothers cannot address their children using the children's personal names. Instead, the mothers use either appellations such as *okò mi'* (my husband) or their children's names. For example, *'bábáa Sadé'* (Sadé's father), *'íyáa Wúmi'* (Wumi's mother). The aim of the adoption of any of these names or systems is essentially to show deference to the son or daughter.

Among the educated parents and children, choice of pronouns is contingent on education and social exposure. Parents use singular pronouns for their children while the children use plural pronouns for their parents. The exchange between a child and his father below sheds more light on pronoun usage.

- Son/Daughter: Ìn pèlẹ̀ bàá mi, kàrí yèe mi. Mè rí òn
 (Greeting to you (plural) my father, where is my mother. I did not see her (plural)).
- Father: Yèe rẹ̀ ròde.
 (Your (singular) mother went out)
- Son/Daughter: Yèe mi, ìn káábò. Bàá mi ìn-ìn ròde
 (My mother, you (plural) are welcome. My father said you (plural) went out).

Although, there are instances where a mother can address her son or daughter 'okò mi' (my husband), it is not done with the aim of showing deference to the son or the daughter. Among the literate or the illiterate mothers, the use of the phrase 'okò mi' (my husband) may also mean an appeal, a greeting or may be adopted in recognition of a good thing done by the addressee without the factor of deference in mind.

Through the use of the second person singular pronoun 'ùwọ' unfavourable comments about a child can be made. For example,

Father: Şé in ti gboludé?

(Have you vacated?)

Child: Họn-ọn

(Yes)

Father: Upò kelòó o şe?

(What is your (singular) position?)

Child: Upò kin-in-ní

(1st position)

Father: Ùwọ?

(You (singular)?)

The adoption of the second person singular pronoun in this context may show either disdain or surprise. This position may be based on lack of seriousness on the part of the child. Another deduction from the pronoun is that the quality of the teaching done in

the school is being questioned, especially if the father's intention refers to disdain. This language use pattern does not go from children to parents. It does not also happen that children would use pronouns as indicators of innuendoes for parents. But the reverse is possible.

Mother: Kári bọọ wà látóúrò

(Where have you (singular) been since morning?)

Child: Sùkúrù

(School)

Mother: Ọ káre. Látóúrò

(You (singular) have really done well, since morning)

Child: Yèsí liijẹ ibèe?

(Who is the owner of this food?)

Mother: Tẹ

(Your (singular) own)

Father: Yèsó i kée wa dè ó?

(Whom did you (singular) ask to prepare the food for you (singular)?)

Mother: Omọ usẹ rẹ ó fińle ni

(His (singular) apprentice whom he has put in the house)

Father: Ó jeun lúlée à fi bọọ bá şàlayé úrin o rin látòúrò

(You (singular) will not eat in this house until you (singular) have explained your (singular) movement since morning).

There are two reasons that can encourage the use of some pronouns as indicators of innuendoes. First, if the addressee has committed an offence or there is a disagreement between the addressee and the speaker. Secondly if the addressee is hard of hearing or the addressee is the type who hears something but pretends not to hear. This pretence or attitude is known as 'àgbóya' in Ijesa.

This language situation can also be observed between two former lovers, people of the same age and husbands and wives. For example,

Husband: Èẹ̀ sùwo òn-òn pè?

(Are you (singular) not the one he/she (plural) or they are calling?)

Wife: Èmi?

(I?)

Husband: Èmi

(I)

The use of the underlined pronoun in this case may mean annoyance or displeasure.

4.9 PRONOUN CHOICE BETWEEN HUSBANDS AND WIVES

The research hypothesis was that between husbands and wives, reciprocal use of singular pronouns is the case. Our findings negate the research hypothesis.

The findings show that two categories of husbands and wives can be identified in the Ijesa speaking area. The first category comprises husbands and wives that are not educated while the second category consists of husbands and wives that are educated.

Between husbands and wives that are not educated, singular pronouns as modes of address are commonly used. For example,

Wife: Q kùàbò. Áá pẹ ọ

(You (singular) are welcome. You (singular) are late in returning)

Husband: Q kúule. Kọọ wá dẹmí?

(You (singular) are greeted for being at home. What did you (singular) prepare as food for me?)

Wife: Bọso oko ọ rán

(Remove your (singular) farm cloth first)

Husband: Mẹ jẹun lóko.

(I did not eat in the farm)

Wife: Èmi náà rò bẹ̀ẹ̀ mọ́ tì wáhun dẹ̀ ọ́.

(I, too, thought of that, I have prepared food for you (singular)).

The difference in the age of men and women is usually disregarded by women in choosing pronouns of familiarity for men. This language use between husbands and wives, which is based on familiarity and intimacy, is evidence of the adage which says 'Eni taa bá sùn ti láá jorunpá lù' (Anybody one sleeps with is the person one stumbles on). Today, in the Yoruba-speaking area, boys and men who are interested in illicit sex with girls or women frown at the use of plural pronouns as modes of address by girls or women in addressing them. They see plural pronouns which perform functions of social distance as pronouns of barrier. Instead, they want to be addressed with singular pronouns which are pronouns of familiarity and which call for equality and closeness.

as the illiterate couples are concerned, is observed in the Yoruba traditional society.

As the topic changes, pronouns that are adopted as modes of address may also change. For example,

Husband: Oó o wí maa rí gbà lúpádé rin-in íkò?

(Where is the money you said I would get from your (plural) meeting (societal group))

Wife: Ó rí ní tin-in?

(Did you not get from your (plural) own (societal group?))

Wife: Oó òbè íkò? On kúkú ti san oó rin-in

(Where is money for soup? After all they have paid your (plural) salary)

Husband: Tin-in íkò?

(What of your (plural) own?)

Deference or respect is not intended in the reciprocal use of plural pronouns in this context. In this context, when a person is addressed with a plural pronoun, it is assumed that the addressee is representing a person or more than one person. So, the use of plural pronouns is not only for the addressee that is physically present but also for other(s) who is or are not physically present during the time of address.

Again, a change in the topic or context may not necessarily mean a change in pronouns. For example,

Wife: Ìn-in nùkàn lẹ̀ mọ̀

(You (plural) are the only one who knows)

Husband: Ẹ̀n-in náà mọ̀ ní?

(Don't you (plural) know also?)

Wife: Ìn moó ojà á

(You (plural) should bring money for the market)

Husband: Ìn gbin-in bá se tán kin-in jẹ mi gbọ

(When you (plural) are ready, you (plural) should let me know).

From the tone of this discussion, plural pronouns which are adopted as modes of address are not meant to show deference to each other but to show that there is a disagreement or discord between the husband and the wife.

Similarly, plural pronouns are commonly used by the educated couples. For example,

Wife: Ìn káàbò

(You (plural) are welcome)

Husband: Ìn kúulé

(You (plural) are greeted for being at home)

Husband: Ìn-òn ọmọ ikó?

(How are the children?)

Wife: Ọn-òn lúlé

(They are at home)

Wife: Ibi in rẹ̀ ikó?

(How was the place you (plural) went?)

Husband: A dúpẹ̀

(We are grateful)

The factor of education can be said to be responsible for the reciprocal use of plural pronouns. If this is the case then how do we distinguish pronouns which express mockery, discord, inference and play from one another? The topic or context of discussion is meant to be considered.

Reciprocal use of plural pronouns is also common between a married woman and a man especially when there are illegal sexual deeds between them.

Woman: Ìn pẹ̀lé

(Greeting to you (plural))

Man: Ìn ẹ̀un. Ìn-ọ̀n ọ̀mọ̀ í kọ̀?

(Thank you (plural). How are the children?)

Woman: Mèé kí in-in lánàá

(I was greeting you (plural) yesterday)

Man: Mé rí in-in

(I did not see you (plural))

In this context any plural pronoun used should be regarded as a pronoun of deception. A woman who uses plural pronouns for a man does so for the purpose of deceiving relatives of her legal husband in order to keep secret her violation of the matrimonial bond. According to the public opinions, reciprocal use of pronouns of deference guarantees social distance and removes suspicion of illegal sexual deeds between a man and another person's wife.

Also, there are occasions when a husband or a wife can adopt first person singular pronoun in reply to a husband's or a wife's demand. For example,

Wife: In káábò

(You (plural) are welcome)

Husband: Kúnlè kímí

(Kneel down and greet me)

Wife: Èmí?

(Me?)

Pride may be deduced from the use of the first person singular pronoun. This conclusion may be based on the following reasons. First, the woman does not see any social difference between the husband and herself. Secondly, the husband and the wife may have the same educational qualification or that the wife's social status may be higher than that of the husband. It is against this background that some boys who want to marry today prefer either girls from the rural areas or girls that have low education who they can control to girls who are in the cities or with higher education who may be difficult to control.

Furthermore, reasons for choice of pronouns remain the same when there is divorce between a wife and her husband. For example, there are occasions when a former husband and a former wife adopt

the use of first and second person plural pronouns for each other; in such cases, the use of the plural pronouns will mean mockery.

A: Áá kí in-in

(We (instead of I) are greeting you (plural))

B: Ìa náà kí in-in

(We too (instead of I) are greeting you (plural)).

A: Ìn-on omọ íkó?

(How are the children?)

B: In şeun

(Thank you (plural))

The use of plural pronouns in this context serves as a reminder of past intimacy, past friendliness and past social interactions. The use of the plural pronouns also shows evidence of strained relationship existing between the two. It is not only the use of plural pronouns that can show that there is a strained relationship between a former husband and a former wife, interpretations from the use of singular pronouns can also show strained relationship between a former

husband and a former wife. This is evident in the use of the third person singular pronoun in the conversation below:

A: *Okò re tẹ̀lẹ̀ ti ñ kólẹ̀*

(Your (singular) former husband is putting up a building)

B: *Ọ̀un?*

(He (singular)?)

Because of the disaffection that exists between the former husband and the former wife, disdain, envy and surprise can be deduced from the use of the third person singular pronoun.

Furthermore, whichever pronouns are employed as modes of address between the two former lovers, negative messages are usually considered. However, in most cases a former husband uses singular pronouns for a former wife and a former wife uses singular pronouns for a former husband. This language use is not limited to the Ijesa people alone. It is also the case among other Yoruba dialect speakers.

4.10 PRONOUN CHOICE BETWEEN THE RICH AND THE POOR OR ANY OTHER PERSON

The hypothesis that was postulated for pronoun exchange between the rich and the poor was that the rich usually receive plural pronouns from the poor, but the poor would be addressed with singular pronouns by the rich. The findings show that a rich person uses both singular and plural pronouns and in most cases, receives plural pronouns. For example,

- | | |
|-------------|---|
| A rich man: | Mo b ^è èrè r ^e lánàá |
| | — |
| | (I asked of you (singular) yesterday) |
| A poor man: | Sémi? |
| | (I?) |
| A rich man: | Úwọ |
| | — |
| | (You (singular)) |
| A poor man: | Émi gan-an wá in délé lánàá |
| | (I also checked you (plural) at home yesterday) |

A rich man: Ón jùsé re

(They did not deliver your (singular) message)

The adoption of the second person singular pronoun, in this context, for the addressed may be as a result of pride. The factor of wealth normally has disregard for age especially when an elderly person is usually in the habit of looking for financial favour from a younger person. Familiarity in that sense breeds contempt.

However, there are occasions when a rich person uses plural pronouns for a poor person.

Rich man: Á kàn rí in-in mó

(We (instead of I) did not see you (plural) anymore)

The use of the plural pronouns in this context may serve as evidence of discontentment with the addressee's behaviour. This may mean that the poor person is passing bye and he has not paid homage to the rich

person or that what the poor person is owing is due for payment. But if there is a disagreement between a rich person and a poor person the poor person, may make use of phrases which have singular pronouns in addressing a rich person. For example "Olóó ʒolórún àṣírí rẹ̀ ló bọ̀" (A rich person is not God but he or she (singular) is only privileged).

4.11 PRONOUN CHOICE BETWEEN VISITORS AND CHILDREN

The hypothesis that was postulated was that visitors adopt singular pronouns as modes of address to children; in turn children adopt plural pronouns as modes of address to visitors. But, the research findings show that the majority of the children if not all usually adopt singular pronouns in addressing visitors.

However, a child that uses singular pronouns for a visitor who is old or a person that is highly regarded in the society may be referred to as ill-mannered or that the child does not understand the Ijesa dialect and will be immediately corrected.

Child: Yèsí ọ mí wá?

(Who are you (singular) looking for?)

Visitor: Bába re

(Your (singular) father)

Father: Ọ gò. In ni ọn í ló fùn àgbàlagbà

(You (singular) are stupid. It is he (plural) they use for an elderly person)

We can draw some conclusions from this example. First, it is the responsibility of the elders in the society to guide against deviations from the cultural rules for the social use of a language especially when there is no disagreement between the speaker and the addressee. Secondly, the knowledge of the rules of speaking in social interactions is not innate but acquired in some cases through corrections.

It would be recalled that the purpose of this chapter was to analyse the findings of the research that was conducted on choice of pronouns in relation to culture among those who speak the Ijesa

dialect. The data that were collected from our respondents were analysed in their various groups. It was discovered that different factors influenced choice of pronouns in social interactions and these factors were responsible for the invalidity of our hypotheses that were previously postulated.

The next chapter summarises the whole thesis.

CHAPTER FIVE**CONCLUSION**

This study deals with the use of Ijesa pronouns in social interactions. The status of Ijesa pronouns in relation to Ijesa culture vis-a-vis modes of address has shown that Ijesa pronouns are in two categories. Ordinarily, some pronouns, when used, show honour either to a second or third person singular. The second category indicates that there are some pronouns which, when used, can show dishonour either to a second or third person singular. The findings show that there is no difference between standard Yorùbá and Ijesa pronouns as far as the issue of disrespect or deference is concerned (see Akindele, 1990, Abiodun, 1992, Oyetade, 1995).

However, the use of plural pronouns in social interactions does not in some cases reflect the socio-cultural values of deference. For example, plural pronouns have been found to be sometimes used to

show mockery, play, disagreement, deception, annoyance, disappointment and inference and the use of the plural pronouns does not always carry the factor of deference or polite distance for the addressee. This finding shows that Akindele (1990), Oyetade (1995) and Olateju's (1997) findings that the use of plural pronouns in social interactions carries deference and polite distance are sometimes correct.

Similarly, the use of singular pronouns in social interactions does not in some cases reflect the socio-cultural values of either contempt or anger. For example, singular pronouns are usually in use in songs, praise-songs and sermons and the use of any of the singular pronouns does not indicate the factor of either contempt or anger for the addressee who may be better than the speaker in terms of any of the sociological factors. This finding also shows that Olateju's (1997) finding that the use of singular pronouns in social interactions shows, among others, contempt and anger is disputable. This cultural feature

is in agreement with the Hebrew, Greek and Arabic systems of address in the temple, church or mosque especially during sermons and in songs (see The Holy Bible, The Holy Quran). We can therefore say that what the case is in Ijesa can also be the case in any language or dialect that is used for Christian or Islamic sermons anywhere in the world.

Furthermore, Brown and Gilman's (1966) study shows that the French language second person singular pronoun *vous*(V) carries a mark of deference and can indicate power when used in social interactions. Our present study has provided additional information that singular pronouns such as 'èmi' (I), 'ùwọ' (you) and 'òun' (she/he), when used in social interactions, do also indicate power.

We have also shown in our findings that the first person singular pronoun 'èmi' (I) does not only serve the purpose of a source or an emitter of action as advanced by Guy and Allen (1976), it can also be adopted in social interactions to show refusal, innuendoes,

questions, responses to questions, ownership, pride, surprise, threat and confirmation.

Similarly, while previous studies either in Yoruba or in any other language do not consider the social functions of any of the first person plural pronouns, the present study has provided useful information that any of the first person plural pronouns can be adopted by a single person essentially to show either a play on words or mockery in social interactions.

Again, Evans-Pritchard (1966), Geertz (1968) Brown and Gilman (1968) claim that wealth, education, occupation, age, identity factors, sex, family relationship, physical strength and social status influence choice of pronouns in social interactions. In our present study, we have provided additional information that misunderstanding, hatred, jealousy, patronage, support, attention, tone, cooperation, favour, unfamiliarity, bad behaviour, knowledge,

stupidity, appreciation, ability and mistaken identity influence choice of pronouns in social interactions.

It is, also, not in all cases that a distinction can be drawn between the social functions of plural pronouns and the social functions of singular pronouns in social interactions. For example, there are occasions when the social functions of singular and plural pronouns can be disdain, questions, surprise, pride, threat, discord, reminder, responses to questions, affront, refusal, confirmation, innuendoes, concern, displeasure, deception and shame. This finding negates or shows the inconclusive nature of Akindele (1990), Abiodun (1992), Oyetade (1995) and Olateju's (1997) studies which make the social functions of singular and plural pronouns two parallel lines that cannot meet.

AREAS FOR FURTHER STUDIES

Since the present study has only focussed on Ijesa pronouns, there is further need for contrastive studies of pronouns of Ife, Ijesa and Ekiti dialects. Such studies may need to find out, for example, whether Adetugbo's (1967) classification of these dialects still holds.

In view of the findings of the present work, which have provided additional information to existing works, there is no doubt that many other Yoruba dialects that have not been investigated previously can be investigated. Adetugbo (1967) has given a hint of such dialects that are in dire need of investigation as the North West and the South East Yoruba dialects.

We believe that the Ijesa dialect has some variants but the number of these variants has not been determined by the present study. A further study can therefore help to identify these variants and also determine the differences that exist in the variants.

Lastly, the role of tones in the Iješa dialect has not been extensively addressed, especially when there is a contraction or assimilation between words that perform the functions of a particle and pronouns that perform the functions of the combination of a pronoun and a habitual tense either in the positive or in the negative. We are of the opinion that this area deserves further attention.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abiodun, M.A. (1992) "On the Restricted Spread of the Honorific Pronoun in Yoruba: A Case Study of Oñdó, Òwò and Òyi Dialects" African Languages and Cultures 5, 2. Pp. 101-111.
- Abimbola, W. (1968) Ijinle Ohun Enu Ifa, Apa Keji. Glasgow Collins.
- Adams, J.B. (1966) "On Expressive Communication in an Egyptian Village" In Language in Culture and Society (ed) Hymes, D. New York Harper and Row, Pp 272-273.
- Adedeji, A.A. (1969) "A Memorandum Containing Recommendations/Suggestions on the Yorùbá Language" Kaaaro Oojire,

- A Report on Yorùbá Orthography
Ministry of Education, Ibadan. Pp.3-8.
- Adeboyeje, A. et al (1987) Eko Ede Yorùbá Ode Oni 3, Lagos
Macmillan.
- Adeoye, C.L. (1979) Àsà àti Ìse Yorùbá, Ibadan: Oxford
University Press.
- Adetugbo, A. (1967) "The Yorùbá Language in Western
Nigeria: Its Major Dialect Areas".
Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation,
Columbia University.
- Adeleye, J.O. (1969) "A Paper", Kaaaro Oojire, A Report
on Yorùbá Orthography. Ministry of
Education, Ibadan. P. 9.
- Afolayan, A. (1969) "Some Neglected Aspects of Yorùbá
Graphology" Kaaaro Oojire, A report
on Yorùbá Orthography. Ministry of
Education, Ibadan. Pp. 21-25.

- _____ (1969) "Comments on the report of the Yorùbá Orthography Committee" Kaaaro Oojire, A Report on Yorùbá Orthography. Ministry of Education, Ibadan. Pp. 26-28.
- Ahukanna, J.G.W. (1990) "Bilingualism and Code-mixing in Language use: The case of Igbo-English Bilinguals" Multilingualism, Minority Language and Languages Policy in Nigeria, Agbor: Central Books Ltd. Pp. 175-185.
- Ajeigbe, O. (1987) "The Language situation in Nigeria and the choice of a lingua Franca" Ife Studies in English. Vol. 1 & 2, pp 71-72.
- Akere, F. (1982) "Language use and Language Attitudes in Yorùbá Sub-urban town: A Sociolinguistic Response to the

- Factors of Traditionalism and Modernity" Anthropological Linguistics, 21 (7), 344-362.
- Akindele, F. (1990) "A Sociolinguistic Analysis of Yorùbá Greetings", African Languages and Cultures 3, Pp. 1-14.
- Akinjogbin, A. (1969) Ewi Iwoyi Glasgow Collins.
- Akinlabi, A.M. (1985) "Tonal Underspecification and Yorùbá Tone". Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis. University of Ibadan.
- Aluko, J.O. (1993) Osomalo: The Early Exploits of the Ijesa Entrepreneur. Ibadan: African Book Builders.
- Arohunmolase, O. (1987) Agbeyewo Idagbasoke Ede ati Akoto Yorùbá lati odun 1800 si 1985. Ibadan: Onibonoje Press.

- Aromolaran, A. and Mustapha, O. (1974) Akomolede Ijinle Yorùbá I. Lagos: Macmillan.
- Atoye, R.O. (1999) "Native - Speaker Perception of Intonation in Yorùbá Zero - Particle interrogative clauses" Papers in English and Linguistics. Vol. 4, Pp 15-23.
- Awobuluyi, O. (1978) Essentials of Yorùbá Grammar. Oxford University Press, Ibadan.
- Babalola, A. (1969) "Tone Marking" Kaaaro Oojire, A Report on Yorùbá Orthography. Ministry of Education, Ibadan. Pp. xxix-xxxi
- Bamgbose, A. (1967) A Short Yorùbá Grammar Ibadan: Heinemann.
- _____ (1990) Fonoloji ati Girama Yorùbá. Ibadan: University Press.

- Bauman, R. & Sherzre, J. (1975) "The ethnography of speaking" Annual Review of Anthropology, Pp. 95-119.
- Bernstein, B. (1968) "Some Sociological Determinants of Perception An Inquiry into sub-cultural differences" In Fishman, J.A. (ed) Readings in the Sociology of Language. The Hague: Mouton and Co. N.V. Publishers.
- Bloomfield, L. (1966) "Literate and Illiterate Speech" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture and Society. New York: Harper and Row.
- Bock, P.K. (1968) "Social Structure and Language Structure" In Fishman, J.A. (ed) Readings in the sociology of

language. The Hague: Mouton and Co. N.V. Publishers.

_____ (1962)

"The Social Structure of a Canadian Indian Reserve" Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation, Harvard University, Cambridge, Mass.

Bourhis, R.Y. and Giles, H. (1976)

"The Language of Cooperation in Wales: A Field Study" Language Sciences Indiana University No. 42 pp 13-16.

Bowen, T.J. (1858)

Grammar and Dictionary of the Yorùbá Language. Washington D. C.; Smithsonian Institute.

Brown, R. and Ford, M. (1966)

"Address in American English" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture

and Society. New York Harper and Row.

Brown, R. and Gilman, A. (1968)

"The Pronouns of Power and Solidarity" In Fishman, J.A. (ed) Readings in the Sociology of Language Mouton & Co. N.V. Publishers. The Hague. Pp. 252-275.

Casagrande, J.B. (1966)

"Comanche Baby Language" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture and Society. New York, Harper and Row.

Chambers, K. and Trudgill, P. (1980)

Dialectology. Press Syndicate of the University of Cambridge.

Chomsky, N. (1957)

Syntactic Structures. The Hague, Mouton and Co.

- _____ (1965) Aspects of the Theory of Syntax.
Cambridge, Mass, MIT Press.
- Conklin, H.C. (1966) "Linguistic Play in its Cultural
Context" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language
in Culture and Society. New York:
Harper and Row. Pp. 295-299.
- Crowther, S.A. (1852) A Grammar and Vocabulary of the
Yorùbá Language, London, Seelay's.
- Ekundayo, S.A. (1976) "On the Sociolinguistic/ Semantic
Boundary" Language Sciences
Indiana University No. 42 pp 6-10.
- _____ (1987) "English in Suppressive Interference"
Ife Studies in English Language Vol.
1 Nos. 1 & 2 pg. 5-13.
- Ervin-Tripps, S. (1973) "An Analysis of the Interaction of
Language, Topic and Listener"
Argyle, M. (ed) Social Encounters
England: Penguin Books. Pp. 65-75.

- Ervin-Tripp, S.M. (1972) "Sociolinguistic Rules of Address" In
Pride, J.B. and Holmes, J. (ed)
Sociolinguistics England: Penguin
Books.
- Ervin, S.M. and Miller, W.R. (1968)
"Language Development" In
Fishman, J.A. (ed) Readings in the
Sociology of Language. Mouton &
Co. N.V. Publishers, The Hague.
- Evans-Pritchard, E.E. (1966)
"Nuer Modes of Address" In Hymes,
D. (ed) Language in Culture and
Society. New York, Harper and Row.
- Falola, T. (1986) "The Ijaye in Diaspora, 1862-1895:
Problems of Integration and Re-
settlement" Annals of the Institute of
Cultural Studies. University of Ife,
Nigeria. Pp 83-99.

- Fasold, R. (1990) The Sociolinguistics of Language
Basil Blackwell Inc. 3 Cambridge
Center Cambridge.
- Ferguson, C.A. (1959)
"Diglossia" Word 15:325-340.
- _____ (1966)
"Diglossia" In Hymes, D. (ed)
Language in Culture and Society.
New York, Harper and Row.
- Firth, J.R. (1966)
"On Sociological Linguistics" In
Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture
and Society. New York, Harper and
Row.
- Fischer, L.J. (1966)
"Social Influences on the Choice of a
Linguistic Variant" In Hymes, D. (ed)
Language in Culture and Society.
New York, Harper and Row.
- Fishman, J.A. (1972)
"The Relationship between Micro and
Macro - Sociolinguistics in the Study
of who speaks what Language to

- whom and when" In Pride, J.B. & Holmes, J. (ed) Sociolinguistics. England: Penguin Books.
- Frake, C.O. (1966) "The Diagnosis of Disease among the Subanun of Mindanao" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture and Society. New York: Harper and Row. Pp. 193-207.
- _____ (1972) "How to Ask for a Drink in Subanun" In Pride, J.B. and Holmes, J. (ed) Sociolinguistics England: Penguin Books.
- Gambhir, S.K. (1983) "Diglossia in Dying Languages: A Case Study of Guyanese Bhojpuri and Standard Hindi" Anthropological Linguistics Vol. 25, No. 1, pp 28-38.

- Garvin, P.L. & Mathiot, M. (1968).
 "The Urbanization of the Guardian Language:" A Problem in Language and Culture". In Fishman, J.A. (ed) Readings in the Sociology of Language. Mouton & Co. N.V. Publishers, The Hague.
- Geertz, C. (1968)
 "Linguistic Etiquette" In Fishman, J.A. (ed) Readings in the Sociology of Language. Mouton & Co. N.V. Publishers, The Hague.
- Goke-Pariola, A. (1987)
 "Towards a Description of the Sociolinguistic Basis of Language Choice in A Nigerian Urban Centre" Ife Studies in English. Vol. 1 & 2 pp 87-98.

- Goodenough, W.H. (1966) "Cultural Anthropology and Linguistics" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture and Society. New York, Harper and Row.
- (1972) "Sociolinguistics and Communication in Small Groups" In Pride, J.B. and Holmes, J. (ed) Sociolinguistics England: Penguin Books.
- Guy, R.F. and Allen, D.E. (1976) "Pronouns, Proximity and the Generalized Other" Language Sciences. Indiana University No. 42 pp 10-12.
- Haas, R.M. (1966) "Interlingual World Taboos" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture and Society. New York, Harper and Row.

- Herzog, G. (1966) "Drum - Signalling in a West African Tribe" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture and Society. New York, Harper and Row.
- Heye, J. (1979) "Bilingualism and Language Maintenance in Two Communities in Santa Catarina, Brazil" In McCormack, W.C. & Wurn, S.A. (ed) Language and Society. The Hague: Mouton & Co. N.V. Publishers. Pp 401-421.
- Hoijer, H. (1966) "Cultural Implications of some Navaho Linguistic Categories" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture and Society. New York, Harper and Row. Pp. 142-149.

- Hymes, D. (ed) (1966) Language in Culture and Society.
New York: Evanston & London:
Harper and Row.
- _____ (1968) "The Ethnography of Speaking: In
Fishman, J.A. (ed) Readings in the
Sociology of Language. Mouton &
Co. N.V. Publishers, The Hague.
- _____ (1974) Foundations in Sociolinguistics: An
Ethnography Approach. University of
Pennsylvania Press. Philadelphia.
- Idowu, E.B. (1962) Olodumare God in Yorùbá Belief.
Ikeja: Longman.
- _____ (1973) African Traditional Religion A
Definition SCM Press. 58.
- Ikotun, R.O. (1995) "Code Choice in Idoani Community
in Ondo State". Unpublished M.A.
Thesis, Obafemi Awolowo
University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

- _____ (1999) "English in Suppressive Interference: More Phonological Data" Papers in English and Linguistics Vol. 4. Pp 106-110.
- _____ (2000) "Yoruba Numeral Qualifiers Revisited" Journal of Black and Asian Affairs, Pp. 48-59.
- Katz, J.J. (1966) The Philosophy of Language. New York: Harper & Row.
- Labov, W. (1968) "The Reflection of Social Process in Linguistic Structures" In Fishman, J.A. (ed) Readings in the Sociology of Language. Mouton & Co. N.V. Publishers, The Hague.
- _____ (1972) "The Study of Language in its Social Context" In Pride, J.B. and Holmes, J. (ed) Sociolinguistics England: Penguin Books.

- Levi-Strauss, C. (1966) "Structural Analysis in Linguistics and in Anthropology" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture and Society. New York, Harper and Row.
- Lotz, J. (1966) "On Language and Culture" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture and Society. New York, Harper and Row. Pp 182-184.
- Marshall, L. (1968) "Sharing, Talking and Giving: Relief of Social Tensions Among/Kung Bushmen" In Fishman, J.A. (ed) Readings in the Sociology of Language. Mouton & Co. N.V. Publishers, The Hague.
- Mustapha, O. et al (1988) Eko Ede Yorùbá Titun Iwe Keta. Ibadan: University Press.

- Nadel, S.F. (1966) "Morality and Language Among the Nupe" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture and Society. New York, Harper and Row. Pp 264-266.
- Nader, L. (1968) "A Note on Attitudes and the Use of Language" In Fishman, J. A. (ed) Readings in the Sociology of Language. Mouton & Co. N.V. Publishers, The Hague.
- Newman, S. (1966) "Vocabulary Levels: Zuni Sacred and Slang Usage" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture and Society. New York, Harper and Row.
- Ogunbowale, P.O. (1970) The Essentials of the Yorùbá Language. Ibadan: Publishers Services.

- Oke, D.O. (1972) "Language Choice in the Yorùbá - Edo Border Area", ODU, New Series No 7.
- Okediji, F.O. & Okediji, O.O. (ed) (1970) The Sociology of the Yorùbá Ibadan: University Press.
- Olabode, A. (1987) "Ìṣowò-lo-òrò-Aròpò orukọ Nínú èdè Yorùbá" Sémínà ní Írántí Olóògbé Ènjinníà karunwì, 24-26, Oṣù kejọ ọdún 1987 ní Yunifasiti ilú Èkó.
- Ọlateju, A. (1997) "A Survey of the Pronoun Usage Situation in the Egba and Ijebu Dialect Areas of Ogun State". Journal of Yorùbá Folklore, CISSN 1117-5559 Vol. 1. Pp 101-107.
- Ọlatunbosun, F. (1991) Igbaradi Fun Idanwo S.S.C. Yorùbá. Ọlatunbosun Publishers. Osogbo.

- _____ (1996) Eto Iro Ati Girama Yorùbá Fun Ile-Iwe Sekondiri Agba. Olatunbosun Publishers, Osogbo.
- Olowookere, T. (1984) Fonetiiki, Fonoloji ati Sintaasi Yorùbá. Monography.
- Omikunle, T. (ed) (1992/93) Osun State Annual Incorporating WHO'S WHO. Lagos: Vision Link.
- Omoniyi, T. (1987) "The Market Value of Code - Alternation and Switching: Socio-Economic Implications of Aspects of Sociolinguistic Variation" Ife Studies in English Language. Vol. 1, Nos. 1 & 2.
- Onibere, S.G.A. (ed) (1980) Ife Journal of Religions. Vol. 1.

- Owolabi, K. (1989) "The Nonexistence of Topical Qualifiers in Yorùbá" Yorùbá Journal of Yorùbá Studies Association of Nigeria. Special Number. Pp. 1-21.
- _____ (1989) Ìjinlẹ̀ Ìtúpàlẹ̀ Èdè Yorùbá Fonetiki ati Fonoloji. Ibadan: Onibonoje Press & Book.
- Owolabi, O. et al (1990) Ìwé Ìgbàradi Fún Ìdánwò Àsekágbà Ilé-Èkó Sèkóndírì Àgbà. Ibadan: Evans Brothers Publishers.
- Oyelaran, O.O. (1971) "Yoruba Phonology Stanford University". Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation.
- _____ (1976-77) "Linguistic Speculations on Yoruba History" Seminar Series, No. 1, Part II. Department of African Languages & Literatures, University of Ife.

- Oyetade, S.O. (1983) "A Survey of Attitudes Towards some Yorùbá Dialects". Unpublished M.A. Thesis, University of Ibadan.
- _____ (1995) "A Sociolinguistic Analysis of Address Forms in Yorùbá" Language in Society Vol. 24, No. 4. Pg. 515-535.
- Peng Fred, C.C. (1976) "Linguistic Innateness; Reply to Bender" Language Sciences. Indiana University No. 42. Pp 34-35.
- Pride, J.B. and Holmes, J. (ed) (1972) Sociolinguistics England: Penguin Books.
- Quirk, R. et al (1972) A Grammar of Contemporary English Essex, Longman Group Ltd.

- Salami, L.O. (1987) "The Social Patterning of Variation in Spoken Yorùbá in Ile-Ife, Nigeria". Unpublished D. Phil Thesis, Brighton: University of Sussex.
- _____ (1999) "Sociocultural Dimensions of Language use among Yorùbá City Dwellers" Papers in English and Linguistics Vol. 4, Pp. 57-64.
- Saville-Troike, M. (1982) The Ethnography of Communication: An Introduction England: Basil Blackwell Publisher.
- Trager, G.L. (1966) "Paralanguage: A First Approximation" In Hymes, D. (ed) Language in Culture and Society. New York, Harper and Row. Pp. 274-277.

- Ure, J. (1979) "Language Choice and Socialization in a Multilingual Community: Language use Among Primary School Teachers in Ghana" In McCormack, W.C. & Wurn, S.A. (ed) Language and Society. The Hague: Mouton & Co. N.V. Publishers.
- Vidal, T. (1986) "The Westernization of African Music: A Study of Yorùbá Liturgical Church Music" Annals of the Institute of Cultural Studies. University of Ife, Nigeria. Pp 70-82.
- Ward, I.C. (1952) An Introduction to the Yorùbá Language. Cambridge, W. Heffer and Sons Ltd.
- Wardhaugh, R. (1986) An Introduction to Sociolinguistics, Oxford: Basil Blackwell Ltd.

Yemitan, O. & Ogundele, O. (1970)

Ojú Òsùpá Apa Keji. Oxford
University Press, Ibadan.

Zengel, M.S. (1968)

"Literacy as A Factor in Language
Change" In Fishman, J.A. (ed)
Readings in the Sociology of
Language. Mouton & Co. N.V.
Publishers, the Hague.

APPENDIX

INSTRUCTIONS: Kindly respond as objectively as possible and tick any answer you consider appropriate.

PART ONE: PERSONAL DATA

1. Sex: Male Female
2. Age:
3. Marital Status: Married Single
4. Can you Read Write?
 Yes/No Yes/No
5. What is your level of education?
 - (a) Primary Six
 - (b) Standard Six
 - (c) Modern Three
 - (d) G. 4
 - (e) WASC
 - (f) Grade Three

- (g) Grade Two []
- (h) B.A. [] M.A. [] Ph.D. []
- (i) No formal education []
6. What is your occupation?
- (a) Farming []
- (b) Trading []
- (c) Civil Service []
- (d) Teaching []
- (e) Artisan []

PART TWO: SURVEY OF IJESA PRONOUNS

1. Which among the Ijesa pronoun(s) do you use in addressing following people when there is no disagreement?

	Plural Pronouns	Singular Pronouns
(a) Husband/Wife	[]	[]
(b) Child	[]	[]
(c) Parents	[]	[]
(d) A married woman who is not your wife	[]	[]

(e)	Boss or head	[]	[]
(f)	Apprentice	[]	[]
(g)	Person of the same status	[]	[]
(h)	An outsider or stranger	[]	[]
(i)	Person who is older	[]	[]
(j)	Person who is younger	[]	[]
(k)	Person who is of the same age	[]	[]
(l)	A Priest or Imam	[]	[]
(m)	A customer	[]	[]
(n)	A former wife/husband	[]	[]
(o)	A girl or boy friend	[]	[]
(p)	A rich person	[]	[]

2. Which pronoun(s) do you use in addressing the following people when there is a disagreement?

	Plural Pronouns	Singular Pronouns
(a) Husband/Wife	[]	[]
(b) Child	[]	[]
(c) Parents	[]	[]
(d) A married woman who is not your wife	[]	[]

(e)	Boss or head	[]	[]
(f)	Apprentice	[]	[]
(g)	Person of the same status	[]	[]
(h)	An outsider or stranger	[]	[]
(i)	Person who is older	[]	[]
(j)	Person who is younger	[]	[]
(k)	Person who is of the same age	[]	[]
(l)	A Priest or Imam	[]	[]
(m)	A customer	[]	[]
(n)	A former wife/husband	[]	[]
(o)	A girl or boy friend	[]	[]
(p)	A rich person	[]	[]

3. Which pronoun(s) do you use as a play on words when addressing the following people?

	Plural Pronouns	Singular Pronouns
(a) Husband/Wife	[]	[]
(b) Child	[]	[]
(c) Parents	[]	[]
(d) A married woman who is not your wife	[]	[]
(e) Boss or head	[]	[]

(f)	Apprentice	[]	[]
(g)	Person of the same status	[]	[]
(h)	An outsider or stranger	[]	[]
(i)	Person who is older	[]	[]
(j)	Person who is younger	[]	[]
(k)	Person who is of the same age	[]	[]
(l)	A Priest or Imam	[]	[]
(m)	A customer	[]	[]
(n)	A former wife/husband	[]	[]
(o)	A girl or boy friend	[]	[]
(p)	A rich person	[]	[]

4. Which pronoun(s) do you use when you are praise-singing any of the following people?

	Plural Pronouns	Singular Pronouns
(a) Husband/Wife	[]	[]
(b) Child	[]	[]
(c) Parents	[]	[]
(d) A married woman who is not your wife	[]	[]
(e) Boss or head	[]	[]
(f) Apprentice	[]	[]
(g) Person of the same status	[]	[]

- | | | | |
|-----|-------------------------------|-----|-----|
| (h) | An outsider or stranger | [] | [] |
| (i) | Person who is older | [] | [] |
| (j) | Person who is younger | [] | [] |
| (k) | Person who is of the same age | [] | [] |
| (l) | A Priest or Imam | [] | [] |
| (m) | A customer | [] | [] |
| (n) | A former wife/husband | [] | [] |
| (o) | A girl or boy friend | [] | [] |
| (p) | A rich person | [] | [] |